

Citation Extraction and Parsing

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Proceedings of the Workshop on Citation Extraction and Parsing

CiteX

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Introduction

These proceedings include the abstracts of the contributions at the Workshop on Citation Extraction and Parsing (CiteX 2026). The workshop provides an interdisciplinary forum for researchers, developers, and practitioners to explore current advances in the automated identification, structuring, and dissemination of bibliographic references, as accurate and open citation data are essential foundations for transparent, reproducible, and networked scholarship.

Building upon the growing momentum around open citations and initiatives such as [WikiCite](#), [WOOC](#), and the [Frankfurt Workshop series](#), CiteX 2026 aims to foster the dialogue across communities working on both the methodological and infrastructural aspects of citation data. By bringing together perspectives from research, infrastructure, and applied contexts, the workshop seeks to strengthen collaboration, identify shared challenges, and promote the development of interoperable and openly accessible citation ecosystems.

CiteX explores topics like creation and sharing of gold standards and test datasets, standardization and interoperability of citation data, quality assessment and validation of extracted references, provision and integration of open citation data into repositories and search systems, citation practices across disciplines, data linking between scholarly works, prompt engineering and fine-tuning of LLMs (e.g., GPT-4, LLaMA) for citation tasks, and comparison of LLM-based and tool-based (e.g., GROBID, Anystyle, Cermine) extraction pipelines.

We thank all participants for their contributions and our committee members for their support. Many thanks to Anele Schmidt, Ana Schenk and Ezgi Tugyan from DIPF for their support of the workshop organization and proceedings publication.

Frankfurt and Cologne, May 2026

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An Iterative OCR and LLM-Based Workflow for High-Accuracy Citation Extraction in Large-Scale Bibliographic Corpora

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Keywords

Citation extraction, OCR, bibliographic data, large language models, digital humanities, reference parsing

Purpose of this paper

The present study describes an iterative workflow for extracting reliable and reusable citation data from complex printed bibliographies that are difficult to process with standard OCR alone. The problem is especially relevant for large domain specific and historical bibliographies whose layout, typography, and editorial conventions vary strongly across volumes and decades. In such material, small recognition errors can invalidate author names, publication years, titles, or page ranges and therefore propagate into matching, deduplication, and linking errors. The paper is situated in the context of the ARTUS DIGITAL project, which is transforming the Bulletin bibliographique de la Société Internationale Arthuriennne / Bibliography of the International Arthurian Society into an openly reusable digital bibliography [1, 3]. The contribution aligns with the aims of CiteX by focusing on automated reference extraction, reproducible workflows, and the preparation of citation data for downstream integration into interoperable scholarly infrastructures.

The paper therefore treats citation extraction not as a single isolated parsing problem but as a chain of dependent transformations in which page layout, recognition quality, and metadata structuring must be optimised together. This perspective is particularly important for humanities bibliographies, where multilingual references, older orthographic forms, nonstandard abbreviations, and visually encoded

boundaries produce failure modes that are rarely captured by pipelines developed for born digital scientific articles.

Method

The workflow follows OCR-D principles and is designed as a modular pipeline with explicit intermediate representations [6]. It begins with scanned page images and combines image preprocessing, layout segmentation, OCR, post correction, and LLM based structured extraction. This design makes the process reproducible while allowing targeted improvement of individual components.

In the preprocessing stage, scans are normalised through binarisation, cropping, deskewing, and resolution control. These steps stabilise page geometry, improve foreground background separation, and reduce border artefacts. Layout analysis is then applied with deep learning segmentation models, including Kraken and eynollah, to identify columns, text regions, and line baselines [4, 8]. This stage is crucial because merged columns, missed regions, and fragmented baselines frequently destroy citation boundaries in densely packed bibliographies.

Text recognition is performed at line level with Calamari [10]. Recognition quality is iteratively improved through project specific fine tuning on manually corrected samples, with correction effort focused on surnames, numerals, punctuation, diacritics, and abbreviations that are most important for citation parsing and later linking. After OCR and post correction, an instruction tuned large language model is used to transform noisy citation strings into normalised bibliographic records with fields such as authors, title, publication venue, year, volume, issue, pages, editors, and notes, following few shot and instruction based extraction logic [2]. A teacher student strategy is used to support scalable deployment: high quality manual corrections and high confidence outputs from the large model are used to fine tune smaller models for more cost efficient batch processing.

Dataset

The current corpus comprises 47 volumes of the bibliography and contains more than 45,000 bibliographic entries [3]. The material is challenging because it is heterogeneous in layout and typographic conventions, includes multilingual references, and often relies on indentation and visual structure rather than explicit delimiters to separate records. These characteristics make the dataset a demanding test case for citation extraction from printed bibliographies and a suitable benchmark environment for iterative OCR improvement.

At the same time, the corpus is large enough to require scalable processing strategies rather than purely manual indexing. The combination of corpus scale and structural irregularity makes it a strong use case for evaluating whether iterative OCR improvement and LLM-supported normalisation can produce citation data that are both operationally useful and suitable for later reuse in linked data environments.

Analysis

Evaluation is organised across multiple processing stages in order to localise failure sources rather than treating extraction as a single end to end task. Recognition accuracy is measured after raw OCR, after image preprocessing, after spelling correction, and after manual correction with model retraining. Based on the reported recognition accuracies, approximate character error rates are calculated as the complementary error rate to provide a compact view of quality development across the pipeline. Structured extraction is further checked against schema requirements for mandatory fields and internal consistency. Because the project aims at 100 percent accuracy for the final bibliographic data, the automated workflow is complemented by human manual correction before final inclusion in the database.

This staged evaluation logic also supports more efficient quality assurance. When errors cluster at a specific step, for example in segmentation or in line recognition, correction effort can be directed to the component that yields the highest downstream benefit. Conversely, when OCR quality is already high but extraction remains unstable, prompts, schemas, and supervision data for the extraction models can be revised without rerunning the entire imaging workflow.

Findings

The current results provide the empirical grounding requested by the review and show a clear improvement trajectory across the OCR workflow. Initial recognition accuracy on the raw material was 78 percent, corresponding to an approximate CER of 22 percent. After preprocessing, recognition accuracy increased to 94 percent and the approximate CER fell to 6 percent, indicating that image normalisation substantially reduces downstream transcription errors.

A subsequent spelling correction step further increased recognition accuracy from 94 percent to 97 percent, reducing the approximate CER from 6 percent to 3 percent. After manual correction of project specific samples and retraining of the OCR model, recognition accuracy reached 99 percent, corresponding to an approximate CER of 1 percent. These gains are significant because the remaining errors are concentrated in exactly those elements that most strongly affect bibliographic parsing and linking, such as author surnames, years, abbreviations, and page references.

Figure 1. Recognition accuracy and approximate CER across preprocessing, spelling correction, and model refinement stages.

The results support the central design assumption of the paper: metadata quality depends directly on OCR quality, and iterative refinement at earlier stages leads to measurable improvement in later structured extraction. They also demonstrate that a modular workflow combining segmentation, recognition improvement, post correction, and LLM based normalisation can make complex printed bibliographies substantially more usable as structured citation data.

In practical terms, the reduction from approximately 22 percent CER to 1 percent CER changes the usability of the corpus fundamentally. At the early stage, noisy output still requires substantial manual intervention before references can be trusted. At the final automated stage, the data quality is high enough to support semi automated indexing, validation, and enrichment workflows. For the final database, however, the project aims at 100 percent accuracy, which requires human manual correction of the remaining difficult cases.

Research limitations/implications

The study currently reports robust OCR oriented improvement figures and corpus scale, but field level extraction accuracy for every bibliographic attribute is still being expanded. The present paper therefore focuses on demonstrating the workflow, the measurable OCR improvements, and the role of manual correction in reaching publication quality data. These limitations do not affect the validity of the workflow itself, but they define the next evaluation steps needed to characterise extraction performance more fully.

Practical implications

The proposed workflow has direct practical value for libraries, digital humanities projects, and scholarly infrastructures that need to convert printed bibliographies into reusable digital resources. By combining OCR D compliant processing, targeted manual correction, and LLM based normalisation, the approach supports scalable retro digitisation while preserving the bibliographic detail required for indexing, export, linked open data integration, and long term reuse [1, 6, 7]. The resulting gold standard data and intermediate annotations can also be reused for future benchmarking and for adapting the pipeline to comparable bibliographic corpora in other research domains.

This is especially relevant for institutions that hold legacy bibliographic resources but lack the staff capacity to transcribe them manually. A reusable workflow of this kind can lower the threshold for bringing specialised printed bibliographies into searchable databases, institutional repositories, or knowledge graph applications, and can support quality controlled retro conversion in settings where both cost efficiency and scholarly precision matter.

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CEC: A Tool for Context-Aware Citation Extraction and Citation Intent Classification from Scholarly PDFs

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Keywords

Citation Extraction, Citation Intent Classification, In-text Reference Pointers, Scholarly PDF Processing, Open Citation Data, Ensemble Learning

Purpose of this paper

The Portable Document Format (PDF) (International Organization for Standardization, 2020) has become, since the advent of the Web, the preferred format for sharing scholarly articles because it preserves publishers' print-like presentation while being easily readable on digital devices. However, since PDF prioritizes human readability over machine interpretability, Information Extraction and Natural Language Processing techniques are required to transform its unstructured content into machine-actionable representations.

In scholarly communication, a key extraction target is the citation network linking research outputs, which supports credit attribution, literature discovery, and reproducibility. Yet most large-scale citation analysis still treats citations as homogeneous links, overlooking the rhetorical and contextual signals that appear where citations are made: within the running text of articles. While reference-list parsing is relatively mature, downstream semantic tasks, such as citation intent classification, require reliable extraction of in-text citations together with sentence-level contexts and, ideally, structural cues such as section headings.

This extended abstract presents a recent work published by OpenCitations¹ (Peroni & Shotton, 2020) and developed within the GraspOS² and GRAPHIA³ projects: the *Citation Extraction and Classification Service* (CEC)⁴, an end-to-end system that extracts in-text citations with their context and classifies citation intents according to the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO) (Peroni & Shotton, 2012).

Design

The CEC pipeline is composed of two main components: *Citation Extraction (CEX)* and *Citation Intent Classification (CIC)*. While CEX extracts in-text citations and their context, CIC assigns a citation intent to each instance.

CEX: PDF Parsing and Citation Extraction Component

The first stage of the CEC pipeline is the Citation Extraction component (CEX), which takes scholarly PDFs as input and produces: (i) a TEI-XML representation encoding bibliographic data (e.g., reference list) and document structure (e.g., sections and paragraphs); (ii) a JSON file that records each in-text reference pointer with its sentence-level citation context and, when available, the enclosing first-level section heading; and (iii) a RDF graph compliant with the OpenCitations Data Model to support semantic interoperability (Daquino et al., 2020). **Figure 1** summarizes these steps.

Figure 1. CEX pipeline.

¹ <https://opencitations.net/>

² <https://graspos.eu/>

³ <https://graphia-ssh.eu/>

⁴ <https://github.com/opencitations/cec.git>

To obtain a structured document representation, CEX builds on a trained version of GROBID, a framework for extracting, parsing and re-structuring raw PDF documents into TEI-encoded XML (Lopez, 2009). In the context of CEC, GROBID was selected for its modular, trainable architecture, and particularly for its ability to detect in-text citation callouts – thereby supporting CEX’s primary objective of capturing in-text citations together with their local context.

GROBID performs parsing through a cascade of sequence-labeling models, where each model’s output becomes the next model’s input, enabling a rich document representation through the combination of multiple lightweight, specialized components. For CEX’s purposes, the key components of the cascade are the segmentation and full-text models. Early experiments showed that retraining segmentation yielded clearer improvements than retraining full text, especially on footnote-rich articles – an underrepresented layout in the original segmentation training data but common in the Humanities, where references often appear in footnotes rather than in a final reference list. Training and evaluation followed five-fold cross-validation on a manually annotated dataset of 227 English-language scholarly PDFs (Soricetti, 2025b).

CIC: Citation Intent Classification Component

The second stage of the CEC pipeline is the Citation Intent Classification (CIC) component, which assigns an intent to each extracted citation context. While citation extraction identifies *where* and *how* references occur in the text, CIC addresses the complementary problem of determining *why* a work is cited by modeling the function it serves in the local discourse of the citing article.

CIC is implemented as a dedicated classification service, whose core inference engine is *CiteFusion* (Paolini et al., 2025), a state-of-the-art ensemble model for citation intent classification, specifically designed for addressing the challenges posed by skewed label distributions that characterize standard benchmark datasets in this domain (Cohan et al., 2019; Jurgens et al., 2018). Within CIC, the original multi-class classification problem is decomposed into a set of one-vs-all binary classification subtasks, each corresponding to a specific citation intent category. For each binary subtask, two complementary pretrained language models (PLMs) are employed: a domain-specific model, SciBERT (Beltagy et al., 2019), optimized for scientific discourse, and a general-purpose model, XLNet (Yang et al., 2019), which captures broader linguistic patterns. Each model is independently fine-tuned to distinguish the target intent from all the remaining classes. For a given citation context, the positive-class probabilities produced by all binary classifiers are then concatenated into a single feature vector and passed to a feed-forward neural network meta-classifier (**Figure 2**), which reconstructs the original multi-class prediction.

Figure 2. Working Dynamics of CiteFusion.

CIC adopts the intent classification schema employed by CiteFusion, grounded in object properties of CiTO (Shotton, 2010) and aligned with standard benchmark datasets such as *SciCite* (Cohan et al., 2019). In particular, CIC classifies citation contexts as providing background information (`cito:obtainsBackgroundFrom`), reusing methods (`cito:usesMethodIn`), or reporting or comparing the cited work’s results (`cito:usesConclusionsFrom`). Furthermore, CIC also employs a *residual* label (`cito:citesForInformation`) for valid contexts that do not reliably align with the three main citation functions.

From an I/O perspective, CIC consumes structured citation-context data (not raw PDF text) and is accessible through both a REST API and a web-based application. Inputs can be provided either as the CEX JSON output or as lists of tuples encoding citation contexts, optionally including first-level section titles. When available, section titles provide additional rhetorical cues that can help disambiguate citation intents (Paolini et al., 2025). CIC supports single-item and batch processing (including compressed archives of multiple JSON inputs) and returns intent-annotated outputs in the same format, preserving unused metadata and reporting the predicted label, meta-classifier confidence, and base binary-model probabilities.

Findings

In this section, we report the results of the two main components of the CEC pipeline.

CEX: Citation Extraction Results

With respect to CEX, **Table 1** reports the performance scores (Micro-F1, Macro-F1, and instance-level recall) obtained in the five-fold cross-validation on a manually annotated dataset of 227 English-

language scholarly PDFs (Soricetti, 2025b). Based on these results, fold-2 was selected as the final segmentation model.

Model	Micro F1	Macro F1	Instance Recall (%)
Fold 1	81.75	65.48	10.87
Fold 2	87.25	84.52	19.57
Fold 3	79.72	67.28	15.22
Fold 4	90.81	81.57	13.04
Fold 5	88.00	83.94	13.95

Table 1. Performance of the GROBID segmentation model across the five cross-validation folds.

For end-to-end evaluation of citation-context extraction, we report results both on a curated CEX Gold Standard of 113 articles (Soricetti, 2025a) and, at scale, on an Open Research Europe⁵ (ORE) corpus filtered to 1,109 articles⁶. We consider two evaluation settings: *WoS* (without section matching), which scores matches using only the REFERENCE (in-text reference pointer) and CITATION (citation context) fields in the generated JSON; and *WS* (with section matching), which additionally requires agreement on the SECTION title. **Table 2** shows a substantial drop under WS, indicating that section-title extraction is the primary bottleneck, likely due to limitations inherited from the underlying GROBID pipeline.

CEX Gold Standard			
	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Wos	0.9016	0.8672	0.8841
WS	0.7909	0.7607	0.7755
ORE Corpus			
	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
Wos	0.9106	0.7115	0.7988
WS	0.6609	0.5164	0.5798

Table 2. Results of CEX evaluation on CEX Gold Standard and ORE corpus.

⁵ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>

⁶ Since ORE does not currently offer a public bulk download for its full corpus, the dataset was assembled programmatically through the platform’s public API endpoints. The procedure is available at: <https://github.com/opencitations/cec/tree/b367ff74591e31595b7f67339677798ac67b9db8/extractor/evaluation/ore>

CIC: Citation Intent Classification Results

CIC is evaluated in both WoS and WS settings⁷, based on the performance of the CiteFusion model, which represents the core inference engine of the classification component. In particular, CiteFusion in WS setting achieves *state-of-the-art* performance (Paolini et al., 2025) on both the SciCite dataset (Cohan et al., 2019), with a Macro-F1 score of 89.60%, and on the ACL-ARC citation dataset (Jurgens et al., 2018), with a Macro-F1 of 76.24%⁸. In **Table 3**, we compare CiteFusion models with representative state-of-the-art models for citation intent classification on the SciCite and ACL-ARC datasets, including *ImpactCite* (Mercier et al., 2021), *CitePrompt* (Lahiri et al., 2023), and *Structural Scaffolds* (Cohan et al., 2019).

SciCite Dataset		
Model	Accuracy (%)	Macro-F1 (%)
<i>CiteFusion (WS)</i>	90.80	89.60
<i>CiteFusion (WoS)</i>	89.73	88.48
<i>ImpactCite</i>	88.13	87.93
<i>CitePrompt</i>	87.56	86.33
ACL-ARC Citation Subset Dataset		
Model	Accuracy (%)	Macro-F1 (%)
<i>CiteFusion (WS)</i>	81.29	76.24
<i>CiteFusion (WoS)</i>	76.98	71.46
<i>CitePrompt</i>	78.42	68.39
<i>Structural Scaffolds</i>	----	67.9

Table 3. Performance comparison between *CiteFusion* and representative state-of-the-art models for citation intent classification on the SciCite and ACL-ARC datasets, reported in terms of Accuracy and Macro-F1.

The scores obtained by CiteFusion confirm the effectiveness of the ensemble framework, particularly in imbalanced settings. Furthermore, the inclusion of section titles as contextual features positively impacts classification performance, supporting the hypothesis that rhetorical context plays a relevant role in disambiguating citation intents. This is particularly evident when comparing Macro-F1 scores in WoS and WS settings across both datasets:

- ACL-ARC: $\Delta = 4.78\%$;
- SciCite: $\Delta = 1.38\%$.

⁷ Here WS indicates that section titles are included in the input sentence, while WoS indicates that they are not. Further details in Paolini et al. (2025).

⁸ A comprehensive overview of the results is provided in Paolini et al. (2025), where different meta-classifiers are evaluated. The study also includes computational instability analyses, as well as an investigation of the role of section titles based on Explainable AI experiments.

Overall, these results show that the CIC component effectively complements the citation extraction stage by providing reliable intent annotations which, together with CiTO object properties, enable a more fine-grained and semantically enriched analysis of citation behavior.

Research limitations/implications

The CEC pipeline is currently limited by section-title extraction, as reflected in the performance drop under strict section-matching evaluation (**Table 2**). Since section information can significantly improve citation intent classification, future work will explore hybrid approaches combining GROBID with LLM-based methods for section heading detection and normalization, supported by a dedicated multilingual gold standard aligned with the Discourse Element Ontology (DEO)⁹.

CEX also inherits limitations from GROBID in handling complex and SSH-specific layouts, such as footnote-based references and irregular document structures. Ongoing work will explore SSH-focused models and hybrid architectures (Zhu et al., 2026), which suggests that LLMs can outperform GROBID on challenging SSH bibliography extraction tasks. However, these results do not extend to in-text citation and context extraction, where full-document processing is technically and computationally demanding.

Finally, the CIC component relies on CiteFusion models trained on benchmark datasets such as ACL-ARC and SciCite, which primarily cover domains including computational linguistics, computer science, natural language processing, and biology/medicine. As a result, the generalization of these models to other domains, such as the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH), is neither guaranteed nor systematically evaluated.

Practical implications

CEC provides an end-to-end pipeline from PDF processing to the generation of RDF data that semantically describe citation acts. In addition to identifying citation links, the system also captures where the citation appears, how it is expressed in context, and which rhetorical function it performs within the citing text.

The resulting data can be integrated into Linked Open Data platforms, incorporated into citation indexes, or used for downstream tasks such as network analysis and large-scale scholarly knowledge graph construction. These applications are further supported by the availability of the system as a REST API and web application, facilitating integration into existing scholarly infrastructures.

⁹ <https://sparantologies.github.io/deo/current/deo.html>

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Why citation processing remains challenging in SSH publications: toward a robust and scalable GRAPHIA Citation Index API

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Keywords

Citation Index, Bibliographic Reference Extraction, Citation Linking, Large Language Models, Social Sciences and Humanities

Purpose of this paper

The development of the SSH Citation Index API within the GRAPHIA¹⁰ project is motivated by the need for robust and scalable methods for bibliographic reference processing, tailored to the specificities of scientific publications in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) (Colavizza et al., 2022). Existing tools and benchmarks have largely been designed around publication practices in STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) domains but fail to adequately capture the heterogeneity of SSH scholarship, which is characterised by multilingual sources, footnote-based citation styles, diverse document layouts, and a strong reliance on books and other non-DOI-centric materials. To address these gaps, GRAPHIA pursues an API-driven approach that supports reusable, modular services for reference extraction and parsing, as well as citation linking, designed to operate reliably across SSH-specific publication formats and languages. Rather than proposing a single end-to-end tool, the SSH Citation Index API adopts a pipeline-oriented and hybrid design, in which different extraction and linking

¹⁰ <https://graphia-ssh.eu/>

strategies can be combined or routed depending on document characteristics such as language, citation placement (end-section vs. footnotes), and layout complexity.

At this stage, the SSH Citation Index API is not presented as a finished system but as an implementation-driven exploration of design choices for SSH-oriented citation services. This paper presents the design and development of the SSH Citation Index API and reports on preliminary implementation work for two core endpoints: (i) reference extraction and parsing, and (ii) citation linking. While the semantic characterisation of citations is recognised as an important enrichment layer for SSH research, it is not yet integrated into the main processing pipeline but is being considered as a prospective extension. Together, these components establish the technical foundation for SSH-oriented citation services within GRAPHIA.

Design

Dataset

The GoTriple corpus¹¹ serves as the first large-scale use case for this API, as references extracted from this corpus will enrich GoTriple and other knowledge graphs within GRAPHIA. It consists of a heterogeneous collection of SSH full texts aggregated from multiple providers, spanning 27 disciplines, multiple languages and diverse publication types. Its scale and diversity make it a challenging but representative testbed, particularly with respect to noisy metadata, complex citation contexts, and incomplete identifiers, while also offering direct integration with an existing SSH knowledge graph.

Reference extraction and parsing

State-of-the-art systems for bibliographic reference extraction and parsing have traditionally combined rule-based heuristics with machine learning to segment and structure reference strings. Popular open-source tools such as GROBID and Anystyle-Parser represent leading solutions in this space, often outperforming other parsers in end-to-end extraction and field segmentation tasks when applied "out of the box." A recent comparative evaluation found that Grobid and AnyStyle achieve the strongest results among a range of open-source pipelines, although combinations of tools can be advantageous depending on the evaluation metrics and corpus characteristics (Backes et al., 2024).

Despite these advances, traditional parsers have limitations when faced with the heterogeneity of SSH publications, especially multilingual references and footnote-centric formats. Early work has pointed to the potential of machine learning models, and more recently large language models (LLMs), for improving both extraction and parsing beyond conventional CRF- or rule-based methods (Sarin &

¹¹ <https://dx.doi.org/10.57967/hf/7669>

Alperin, 2025). Initial studies suggest that transformer-based models can generalise across citation styles and languages when provided with appropriate annotated corpora.

Citation linking

Citation linking refers to the process of resolving a bibliographic reference to a corresponding record in one or more external bibliographic databases. Operationally, this task involves generating candidate records based on reference metadata, scoring and disambiguating these candidates using similarity signals, and deciding whether a reliable match can be established or whether the reference should remain unlinked. Each step is sensitive to noise, missing fields, and variation in citation practices, making citation linking a critical but fragile component of large-scale bibliographic infrastructures.

Methodologically, citation linking can be approached through a combination of heuristic matching, classical similarity measures, and, increasingly, embedding-based techniques. Vector representations of references and candidate records enable more flexible matching under noisy and multilingual conditions, making embedding-based similarity a particularly promising direction for SSH-oriented citation linking.

Previous studies consistently show that a substantial proportion of SSH references—typically between 50% and 60%—cannot be linked to existing citation databases (Boulanger et al., 2025; Kokash et al., 2024). Publications in GoTriple are no exception to this trend: out of a random sample of 5,000 GoTriple publications, less than 60% of them could be found (i.e., looked up) in OpenAlex. While the exact figures vary across disciplines, the overall pattern points to systematic gaps in the coverage of SSH literature, particularly for books, chapters, non-English publications, and older works. These findings highlight structural limitations of current citation databases rather than purely algorithmic shortcomings.

Within the SSH Citation Index API, citation linking is planned to target several complementary data sources: OpenCitations¹², Matilda¹³ (including Crossref data), Wikidata¹⁴, and OpenAlex¹⁵. Together, these sources offer broad disciplinary and multilingual coverage, authority control, and open access to identifiers and metadata.

Findings

As far as reference extraction and parsing are concerned, we have undertaken a systematic benchmarking effort that evaluates a variety of LLMs under few-shot and supervised fine-tuning

¹² <https://opencitations.net/>

¹³ <https://matilda.science/>

¹⁴ <https://wikidata.org/>

¹⁵ <https://openalex.org/>

regimes against a benchmark designed to reflect SSH publications' diversity (Zhu et al., 2026). This includes assessing performance on reference segmentation and metadata field extraction, comparing these results against baseline parsers, and analysing how structured prompts or task-specific tuning can mitigate errors common in SSH contexts. This empirical study provides a foundation for selecting and integrating robust parsing components within the SSH Citation Index API.

Reference extraction and parsing within the SSH Citation Index API are implemented as a multi-step process that explicitly separates document segmentation from reference string parsing. This design choice reflects the structural diversity of SSH publications, where references may appear either in end-of-document bibliographies or embedded within footnotes and other non-standard layouts. Rather than relying on a single end-to-end extraction strategy, the pipeline allows different tools and models to be combined depending on document characteristics such as language, layout complexity, and citation placement. This modular approach enables experimentation with both established rule-based tools and large language models, while preserving a consistent API interface for downstream services. Early implementation work suggests that pipeline configuration and segmentation strategies have a significant impact on robustness, particularly for footnote-heavy and multilingual documents, even before considering model-level optimisation.

Research implications

Reference extraction and parsing remain areas of ongoing development. While the current work establishes a modular, pipeline-oriented approach and explores the use of different segmentation strategies, further work is required to consolidate evaluation under SSH-typical conditions. In particular, the availability of suitable benchmark datasets remains limited, especially with respect to multilingual full texts, footnote-based citations, and heterogeneous document layouts.

A further aspect concerns citation linking. While the current implementation focuses on establishing reliable links in the context of heterogeneous and incomplete metadata, systematic evaluation at scale is not yet supported. We are therefore considering the development of an SSH-oriented benchmark dataset for citation linking, with the aim of capturing SSH-specific citation characteristics such as multilingual references, book- and chapter-centric citations, and the frequent absence of persistent identifiers.

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Stackable Citation Knowledge: Building on Nanopublications for Climate and Biodiversity Research

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Keywords

nanopublications, CiTO, stackable knowledge, systematic reviews, FAIR data, LifeWatch ERIC, FAIR2Adapt, climate adaptation, biodiversity, agroecology, LLM extraction, knowledge graphs

Purpose of this paper

Citation data serves two fundamentally different purposes: crediting prior work and enabling others to build upon it. In the academic world, current citation practices excel at the former but fail at the latter. When researchers cite a paper, they reference an entire document rather than a specific claim, method, or dataset. This makes it impossible for others to precisely identify, validate, and extend the atomic units of knowledge that advance science.

Traditional citations treat scholarly works as monolithic units. A paper citing another provides no machine-readable indication of *what* is being cited, whether a specific finding, methodological approach, dataset, or merely background context. This imprecision creates fundamental barriers to scientific progress: researchers cannot reliably build upon prior work because they cannot identify exactly which claims have been validated, disputed, or extended; systematic reviews cannot trace the provenance of findings; and AI systems cannot construct reliable knowledge graphs because citation relationships lack semantic precision.

Nanopublications address this challenge by decomposing research outputs into atomic, independently citable units. Each nanopublication contains a single assertion with its supporting evidence and complete provenance information, creating building blocks that others can stack, combine, and extend (Groth et al., 2010 [*citesAsAuthority*]). When combined with CiTO's vocabulary of citation intents (*extends*, *usesMethodIn*, *disputes*, *citesAsEvidence*), researchers can create precise, machine-actionable links enabling genuine knowledge accumulation (Shotton, 2010 [*usesMethodIn*]).

This contribution presents ScienceLive, a platform (<https://platform.sciencelive4all.org/>) that transforms citation relationships into stackable knowledge units using nanopublications and the Citation Typing Ontology (CiTO). We demonstrate its applications in biodiversity research through LifeWatch ERIC and climate change adaptation through FAIR2Adapt, with agroecology as a bridging domain.

Method

ScienceLive implements a three-layer architecture for stackable citation knowledge, building directly on the foundational nanopublication structure (Groth et al., 2010 [*usesMethodIn*]): an Assertion layer capturing atomic scientific claims as RDF triples linked to Wikidata entities; a Provenance layer using PROV-O to document how assertions were derived from search strategies through screening to final inclusion; and a Publication Info layer providing metadata including creator attribution, timestamps, and CC-BY 4.0 licensing. Each nanopublication receives a Trusty URI containing a cryptographic hash, ensuring integrity and providing globally unique identification resistant to tampering (Kuhn et al., 2021 [*usesMethodIn*]). The decentralized nanopublication network provides persistence without dependence on any single institution (Kuhn et al., 2021 [*citesAsPotentialSolution*]).

LLM-Assisted Nanopublication Generation

A key innovation in ScienceLive is the use of LLMs for semi-automated nanopublication generation. Traditional extraction tools such as GROBID and Anystyle excel at parsing reference strings from PDF documents but cannot determine citation intent. LLMs fill this gap by identifying contextual clues that reveal whether an author cites a work to extend it, dispute it, or simply acknowledge it. Our hybrid pipeline combines traditional tools for reference extraction with LLMs for intent classification, generating JSON configurations that produce AIDA-compliant statements (Atomic, Independent, Declarative, Absolute) linked to Wikidata entities. This approach uses LLMs for what they do best: extracting and structuring information that already exists in human-authored text, rather than producing AI-generated material.

Zotero Integration

We also developed a Zotero plugin enabling researchers to create nanopublications directly from their reference manager. Researchers can annotate citations with CiTO types and register claims to the nanopublication network without leaving their familiar workflow, lowering the barrier to adoption significantly.

Findings

Case studies across three research domains demonstrate the practical value of stackable citation knowledge.

In **biodiversity research**, LifeWatch ERIC provided the context for a PRISMA-compliant systematic review (Page et al., 2021 *[usesMethodIn]*) on quantum computing applications for biodiversity. This produced 238 nanopublications with full CiTO typing and PROV-O provenance chains (Fouilloux, 2025 *[citesAsDataSource]*), demonstrating that atomic, typed citations enable knowledge accumulation across taxonomic groups, geographic regions, and temporal scales.

In **climate change adaptation**, the FAIR2Adapt project (Horizon Europe) adopted nanopublications as a key implementation tool for FAIR Digital Objects, using semantic bridging strategies to build interoperable data-sharing frameworks. CiTO typing enables researchers to identify precisely which climate projections, vulnerability assessments, or adaptation measures they are building upon.

In **agroecology**, LifeWatch ERIC's Agroecology Partnership project demonstrates how stackable nanopublications can bridge traditionally siloed communities. When a climate scientist cites an agroecological intervention study, CiTO typing specifies whether they are using its methodology, building on its findings, or extending its geographic scope (Peroni & Shotton, 2012 *[usesMethodIn]*).

As a meta-demonstration, this paper itself is represented as nanopublications. Rather than simply listing references, we specify as nanopublications exactly which claims we build upon from each cited work. Each citation in this paper carries an inline CiTO type and links in the reference list to the corresponding published nanopublication on the nanopublication network. The complete set comprises 21 nanopublications (7 AIDA cited claims + 6 CiTO citation relations + 8 Wikidata concept definitions).

ScienceLive's architecture inherently satisfies FAIR principles: nanopublications are Findable through Trusty URIs and network indexing; Accessible via the decentralized server network with no authentication barriers; Interoperable through RDF encoding and standard ontologies (CiTO, PROV-O, FaBiO, Wikidata) (Peroni & Shotton, 2012 *[usesMethodIn]*); and Reusable under CC-BY 4.0 licensing with complete provenance. This positions ScienceLive as infrastructure supporting EOSC integration and the broader European Open Science agenda.

Research limitations/implications

Two interconnected trust challenges face the current approach. The first concerns LLM-assisted extraction: when LLMs read papers to identify citation intent or extract claims, they can hallucinate, attributing statements to a source that does not actually contain them, or mischaracterising the nature of a citation relationship. Ideally, authors themselves would validate LLM-generated nanopublications at submission time, confirming that each extracted claim and CiTO predicate accurately reflects their intent. Tooling to support this author-side validation step remains an open challenge.

The second challenge concerns the verification of claims once published. Currently, nothing prevents a researcher from asserting a CiTO predicate that does not accurately describe their citation, or from publishing a nanopublication whose scientific claim is incorrect. Such errors could propagate through

the network as others build upon unchecked assertions. The atomicity of nanopublications is a structural advantage here: because each unit contains a single claim, it is far easier to verify or dispute than a monolithic paper. Nevertheless, the community needs explicit mechanisms for marking claims as verified or contested.

We are beginning to address this through the FORRT replication framework (Röseler et al., 2025 [*citesAsRecommendedReading*]), which provides a structured pathway for verifying published claims. A nanopublication that has been independently replicated or confirmed carries demonstrably more epistemic weight when cited, and ScienceLive is developing support for linking verification studies directly to the original claim nanopublications. This creates a trust gradient, ranging from unverified LLM-extracted assertions through author-validated claims to independently replicated findings, that could become a meaningful signal for how others choose to build upon and cite scientific knowledge.

Practical implications

Beyond academia, richer and more precise citation data would strengthen key use cases that rely on high-quality extraction and parsing. Funding agencies could move beyond coarse productivity metrics toward more accurate impact assessment of specific contributions. Universities would gain better tools to detect emerging topics and research trends through semantic citation networks. Industry stakeholders could more effectively identify foundational advances with clear provenance, supporting knowledge transfer from theory to application.

ScienceLive provides concrete infrastructure for open citation data through the decentralized nanopublication network. The Zotero plugin offers an immediately adoptable tool for researchers to produce typed, machine-actionable citations within their existing workflow. The hybrid LLM pipeline scales the creation of stackable knowledge units, making systematic review workflows tractable at a scale not previously possible with manual approaches.

For the CiteX community specifically, ScienceLive demonstrates practical paths toward standardization and interoperability (via CiTO and SPAR ontologies), quality assurance (via cryptographic verification and provenance tracking), provision of open citation data (via the nanopublication network), and LLM applications for citation extraction and intent classification. We propose a live demonstration of the complete workflow from paper to published nanopublications at the workshop.

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RenoBench: A Citation Parsing Benchmark

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Figure 1: An example annotated citation from RenoBench

Keywords

citation parsing; bibliographic reference extraction; evaluation benchmark; scholarly metadata; large language models

Introduction

Despite sustained interest in machine readable citations (CiteX, 2026; Di Giambattista & Heibi, 2025; OpenCitations, 2025; Weimer et al., 2025), there is currently no community-accepted dataset to evaluate citation parsing. To assist the community working on this task, we introduce the Reference Annotation Benchmark (RenoBench):¹⁶ a standardized evaluation benchmark for citation parsing, which we define as the task of annotating a plain-text reference with structured components following the JATS standard (ANSI/NISO Z39.96-2024: JATS: Journal Article Tag Suite, 2024).

Existing benchmarks typically follow one of three patterns: First, many evaluations rely on small, hand-annotated datasets derived from a single discipline or venue (often computer science or biomedicine)

¹⁶ <https://huggingface.co/datasets/public-knowledge-project/ref-annotation-benchmark>

such as those used to evaluate tools like GROBID and CERMINE (Lopez, 2009; Tkaczyk et al., 2018). Second, recently, synthetic citation datasets like GIANT have emerged which are designed to maximize coverage of citation styles (Grennan et al., 2019). These datasets have been shown to be useful in training contexts (Atanassova et al., 2020), but synthetic references do not capture noise introduced by PDF extraction, multilingual syntax conventions, and publisher-specific production workflows encountered in practice (Lipinski et al., 2013). Third, many citation parsers are evaluated on private datasets, limiting reproducibility (Tkaczyk et al., 2018).

In contrast, RenoBench was assembled by extracting plain-text references from public domain PDFs from multiple journals. To our knowledge, RenoBench is the first public domain citation parsing benchmark sourced from real-world, multi-ecosystem conditions. With its release, we hope to complement existing datasets and enable reproducible comparison of citation parsing systems under realistic operating conditions (Atanassova & Bertin, 2024).

Methodology

Data Sources

Article PDFs and their JATS XML annotations were derived from four publication platforms: SciELO, Redalyc, PKP, and Open Research Europe (ORE). The latter two, PKP and ORE, are publicly available (European Commission, 2025; Garnett, 2016). JATS XML files from Redalyc and SciELO were obtained through communication with these platforms in February and April 2025, respectively.

We obtained the PDF files associated with the JATS XML for each corpus. ORE maintains a public index of XML and PDF URLs;¹⁷ the PKP corpus contains PDF versions of each article; and Redalyc and SciELO have publicly available PDFs at predictable URLs associated with each DOI. We then converted PDFs to markdown using `markdown` (Microsoft Corporation, 2025), a lightweight conversion utility widely used to generate unstructured inputs to language models.

Parsing and Matching

Plain-text citations were extracted from the markdown using `Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct`, programmatically verifying that the extracted citations appeared in the input text to prevent hallucinations. These plain-text citations were then matched to the annotated citations in the corresponding JATS XML files. Plain-text citations p were matched to text-only (stripped) XML citations c in order of decreasing similarity, where similarity is defined as

$$s(p, c) = 1 - \frac{d(p, c)}{\max(|p|, |c|)}$$

¹⁷ <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/published-xml-urls>, <https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/about/developers>

$d(p, c)$ is the edit distance between p and c , and $|s|$ denotes the number of characters in a string s . All matches with similarity less than 0.75 were excluded. This extraction and reconciliation procedure is described in more detail by (sarin & Alperin, 2025). This matching resulted in a total of 161,625 data points.

Filtering

We applied a suite of automated quality checks to remove citations with structural or content errors that would introduce noise into the benchmark. These checks fall into three categories:

1. *Structural validation checks* ensured well-formed XML (e.g., parseable markup, no namespace pollution) and sufficient annotation depth (citations with ≤ 2 meaningful elements were excluded).
2. *Field-level validation checks* asserted regex-style heuristics against fields, detecting invalid dates (e.g., years with letter suffixes like “2020a”, months > 12); problematic page numbers (e.g., reversed ranges where $lpage < fpage$, extreme values $> 10,000$ suggesting DOI fragments, or identical start and end pages); field confusion (e.g., years appearing in author fields, URLs in title fields); and author anomalies (e.g., initials stored as surnames, “et al.” parsed as an author name).
3. *Content consistency checks* aligned the structured annotation and the plain-text citation by fuzzy matching extracted surnames, sources, and article titles against the plain-text.

Of the 161,625 matched citation pairs, 115,193 (71.3%) passed all quality checks. The most common failure reasons were missing page numbers for journal articles (27.7% of errors) and reversed page number ranges (14.4%). We excluded citation pairs that failed these checks.

Sampling and Composition

To construct a dataset capturing a range of contexts, we sought to balance the mix of cited languages, citing and cited publication types, presence of persistent identifiers (PIDs), and publication platform. To impute the cited article language, Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct was used to return the two-letter ISO 639 language code based on the article title. The same model and input were also used to identify whether the citation contained a PID. Each citation was then represented as a binary feature vector encoding PID presence, preprint status, title language (one-hot), publication type (one-hot), and citation source (one-hot).

Rather than sample uniformly, we optimized sampling weights to balance across these features using the following procedure: Let N be the number of total citations and let $f_i \in R^d$ be the feature vector for the i th data point, x_i . Take $\lambda \in R^d$ to be a learnable collection of parameters. Assign a softmax sampling weight to each data point $w_i \leftarrow \exp(\lambda^T f_i)$, so that the probability that x_i is sampled in the first round is

$$p_i(\lambda) = \frac{\exp(\lambda^\top f_i)}{\sum_{j=1}^N \exp(\lambda^\top f_j)}$$

Then, define the aggregate feature vector to be $\mu(\lambda) = E_{i \sim p}[f_i] = \sum_{i=1}^N p_i(\lambda) f_i$, intended to represent a “soft” sample, differentiable with respect to λ . A loss function $L(\mu)$ was then designed to encourage adequate representation/balance. After 1,963 steps at learning rate 10^{-3} , convergence was reached and the final dataset, which contains 10,000 citations, was sampled.

Dataset Composition

The resulting benchmark dataset has the following composition:

- 59% of citations include a persistent identifier (PID)
- 14% of the citing articles are preprints
- Citations span eight languages, with English (32%), Portuguese (30%), and Spanish (23%) most common, followed by French (7%), German (3%), Italian (2%), Russian (2%), and Chinese (1%)
- Publication types include journal articles (53%), books (30%), website pages (8%), theses (5%), and conference proceedings (4%)
- Documents are sourced from four platforms: SciELO (47%), Redalyc (24%), ORE (14%), and PKP (14%)

Evaluation

Several models were evaluated on RenoBench, including GROBID (Lopez, 2009), Qwen2.5 (Yang, Yang, et al., 2025), Qwen3 (Yang, Li, et al., 2025), Mistral (Jiang et al., 2023), Gemma (Gemma et al., 2025), Llama (Grattafiori et al., 2024), and GPT-OSS (OpenAI et al., 2025). The largest model tested was Qwen3-32B and the smallest was GROBID. We evaluated each of the language models by running inference on the Stanford Marlowe compute cluster (Kapfer et al., 2025) with a prompt that provided two annotated examples of citations that were not included in the benchmark. GROBID was evaluated by querying its web API hosted on Hugging Face Spaces. We also evaluated a fine-tuned version of Qwen3-0.6B produced by (COMET, 2025) following the procedure described in (sarin & Alperin, 2025). Table 1 shows the recall accuracy of different models for different markup fields.

We believe that precision is an unreliable metric on this dataset because the JATS XML often omits valid markup elements that models correctly produce. We evaluated all the models for precision and manually reviewed 330 randomly sampled errors. We found that correct annotations were being marked as incorrect due to incomplete ground truth 92% of the time for the *year* field, 85% for the *source* field, and 72% for the *article-title* field. For completeness, we still report precision in Table 2.

Tables 1 and 2 report accuracy where, even if the model produced malformed XML, we still considered assertions for fields if they appeared between valid XML tags (e.g., `<year>2026</year>` may be asserted even if the `<mixed-citation>` tag is not closed). Tables 3 and 4 report stricter recall and precision metrics, which do not consider those assertions, such that field-level accuracy is bounded above by the valid XML percentage.

Finally, we attempted to optimize the prompt using GEPA (Agrawal et al., 2025), using recall on a held-out training subset as the optimization objective. Prompt optimization did not yield consistent or meaningful improvements over the baseline prompts for any of the evaluated models so we do not report these results.

Table 1. Recall Across Models and Fields

Model	Valid XML	Surname	Given	Title	Source	Volume	Issue	Year
GROBID	100.0	71.6	18.8	65.2	51.8	90.0	86.8	97.9
Qwen/Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct	83.5	93.0	64.1	93.9	54.3	95.5	83.8	93.8
Qwen/Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct	87.6	95.8	74.5	94.0	53.3	96.0	86.9	90.6
Qwen/Qwen3-0.6B	81.4	87.3	62.7	84.7	50.6	92.4	92.7	91.7
Qwen/Qwen3-0.6B + cometadata/citation-parsing-lora	95.0	92.6	77.9	93.4	73.3	98.6	95.3	97.2
Qwen/Qwen3-8B	78.2	86.6	70.9	82.0	51.2	90.6	89.8	80.7
Qwen/Qwen3-32B	78.4	86.8	69.2	84.7	55.6	92.3	90.5	86.2
google/gemma-3-1b-it	27.7	84.9	52.5	44.5	37.4	70.9	64.0	69.8
meta-llama/Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	80.3	82.4	58.6	92.7	57.3	98.1	96.0	94.5
mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	86.0	85.4	69.0	91.9	52.8	95.8	94.3	91.6
openai/gpt-oss-20b	88.3	89.1	67.0	93.1	57.4	98.1	96.5	96.7

All values represent recall (%) on field extraction from bibliographic citations.

Bold indicates best performance in each column.

Valid XML shows the percentage of examples producing well-formed, parseable XML.

Field extraction uses a parser with regex fallback to recover fields from malformed XML.

Edit distance thresholds: surname/year/volume/issue = 0 (exact), source = 5, title = 10.

Conclusion

RenoBench provides the first public domain benchmark for evaluating citation parsing under real-world scholarly publishing conditions. Our hope is that it will enable more meaningful and transparent comparisons of reference markup systems that are grounded in references that are noisy, heterogeneous, and multilingual. In presenting our RenoBench, our own evaluations highlight how language models perform on this task relative to established tools and demonstrate the promise of small, domain-specific language models for citation parsing. We see RenoBench as a foundation for future work on improved models and downstream citation indexing applications. If the benchmark proves useful, we propose that

it be expanded with higher-fidelity ground truth (i.e., with more detailed JATS tagging) to support more reliable precision evaluation.

Practical implications

The results presented here have several implications for platforms and organizations engaged in citation parsing work.

The most immediate and actionable finding is that fine-tuning small language models allows them to match or exceed the performance of those many times their size. For those engaged in large-scale citation parsing and specifically where this work may be compute constrained, our results suggests that use of small, fine-tuned models represent a viable and cost-effective alternative to more resource-intensive approaches.

Our findings also highlight an opportunity to address challenges with language diversity in citation parsing. Existing citation parsing tools have primarily been developed using English-language corpora, whereas a substantial proportion of the world's scholarly output is published in languages other than English. The multilingual composition of Renobench provides a basis for identifying whether new and existing methods succeed at parsing non-English citations. Given that our results found that small, fine-tuned models performed well on this task, additional training may allow for the production of language-specific or multilingual models tailored toward the needs of communities and platforms underserved by existing methods. We see this as an important direction for future work, as well as for measuring progress toward a more equitable representation of the global scholarly record.

At the same time, our results also revealed some persistent challenges in the production of valid XML. While GROBID produces well-formed output 100% of the time, even the best-performing language model fell short of this, achieving only a 95% success rate, with several models produce valid markup for less than 80% of inputs. In production systems, these malformed outputs require various forms of fallback parsing or manual intervention, such that these associated costs should be weighed alongside field-level accuracy when selecting a parsing approach.

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Appendix

Table 2. Precision Across Models and Fields

Model	Valid XML	Surname	Given	Title	Source	Volume	Issue	Year
GROBID	100.0	70.2	18.7	58.4	48.0	69.8	49.1	96.9
Qwen/Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct	83.5	86.5	62.5	56.0	53.4	86.7	88.0	97.7
Qwen/Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct	87.6	89.0	72.3	59.2	53.0	87.1	78.3	98.2
Qwen/Qwen3-0.6B	81.4	79.5	59.0	51.1	47.4	42.9	25.7	95.1
Qwen/Qwen3-0.6B + cometadata/citation-parsing-lora	95.0	83.6	73.5	55.7	66.9	43.5	25.2	96.4
Qwen/Qwen3-8B	78.2	91.8	76.1	60.2	59.1	82.3	74.5	91.4
Qwen/Qwen3-32B	78.4	89.5	71.8	60.9	59.7	86.4	78.2	92.4
google/gemma-3-1b-it	27.7	81.3	49.8	41.1	48.2	57.6	34.1	94.5
meta-llama/Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	80.3	79.2	58.3	60.7	59.1	85.4	74.3	98.4
mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	86.0	85.2	69.3	61.0	65.2	88.7	71.7	97.8
openai/gpt-oss-20b	88.3	85.1	65.8	60.1	57.7	88.4	84.8	98.2

All values represent recall (%) on field extraction from bibliographic citations.

Bold indicates best performance in each column.

Valid XML shows the percentage of examples producing well-formed, parseable XML.

Field extraction uses a parser with regex fallback to recover fields from malformed XML.

Edit distance thresholds: surname/year/volume/issue = 0 (exact), source = 5, title = 10.

Table 3. Recall (Strict) Across Models and Fields

Model	Valid XML	Surname	Given	Title	Source	Volume	Issue	Year
GROBID	100.0	71.6	18.8	65.2	51.8	90.0	86.8	97.9
Qwen/Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct	83.5	79.0	54.9	81.6	47.0	84.1	73.5	79.2
Qwen/Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct	87.6	83.7	65.2	83.4	47.1	85.0	76.7	79.8
Qwen/Qwen3-0.6B	81.4	72.5	52.9	72.7	44.2	80.8	81.8	75.8

Model	Valid XML	Surname	Given	Title	Source	Volume	Issue	Year
Qwen/Qwen3-0.6B + cometadata/citation-parsing-lora	95.0	88.5	74.6	89.3	70.1	94.3	91.0	92.8
Qwen/Qwen3-8B	78.2	72.5	60.3	73.0	45.6	78.0	77.6	70.5
Qwen/Qwen3-32B	78.4	74.0	59.5	75.9	50.0	81.0	78.0	74.2
google/gemma-3-1b-it	27.7	21.8	13.5	7.6	6.1	11.9	11.0	13.8
meta-llama/Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	80.3	65.7	45.6	69.6	43.8	73.7	72.5	76.0
mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	86.0	74.6	60.6	80.9	46.8	85.3	82.5	79.4
openai/gpt-oss-20b	88.3	78.7	59.1	80.8	49.2	83.0	82.1	85.9

All values represent recall (%) on field extraction from bibliographic citations.

Bold indicates best performance in each column.

Valid XML shows the percentage of examples producing well-formed, parseable XML.

Field extraction uses a parser with regex fallback to recover fields from malformed XML.

Edit distance thresholds: surname/year/volume/issue = 0 (exact), source = 5, title = 10.

Table 4. Precision (Strict) Across Models and Fields

Model	Valid XML	Surname	Given	Title	Source	Volume	Issue	Year
GROBID	100.0	70.2	18.7	58.4	48.0	69.8	49.1	96.9
Qwen/Qwen2.5-3B-Instruct	83.5	73.4	53.5	48.7	46.2	76.4	77.1	82.5
Qwen/Qwen2.5-7B-Instruct	87.6	77.8	63.2	52.5	46.8	77.1	69.1	86.5
Qwen/Qwen3-0.6B	81.4	66.1	49.8	43.9	41.4	37.5	22.6	78.6
Qwen/Qwen3-0.6B + cometadata/citation-parsing-lora	95.0	79.9	70.4	53.3	64.1	41.6	24.0	92.0
Qwen/Qwen3-8B	78.2	76.8	64.7	53.6	52.6	70.8	64.4	79.8
Qwen/Qwen3-32B	78.4	76.3	61.7	54.6	53.7	75.8	67.4	79.6
google/gemma-3-1b-it	27.7	20.8	12.8	7.0	7.9	9.6	5.8	18.6
meta-llama/Llama-3.1-8B-Instruct	80.3	63.1	45.4	45.6	45.2	64.2	56.2	79.1
mistralai/Mistral-7B-Instruct-v0.2	86.0	74.5	60.9	53.7	57.7	79.0	62.7	84.8
openai/gpt-oss-20b	88.3	75.1	58.0	52.2	49.4	74.8	72.2	87.2

All values represent recall (%) on field extraction from bibliographic citations.

Bold indicates best performance in each column.

Valid XML shows the percentage of examples producing well-formed, parseable XML.

Field extraction uses a parser with regex fallback to recover fields from malformed XML.

Edit distance thresholds: surname/year/volume/issue = 0 (exact), source = 5, title = 10.

Reference Extraction In The Bibliometric Hinterlands: Recovering From Domain Switch With GROBID

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scientific references extraction; research project reports

Introduction

The open access and wider open science movements have changed not only how research is executed and published but also how research information –in particular publication metadata– is created and used. One momentous transformation is the increasing availability of freely accessible and usable cited references data.

Academic publishers have largely been convinced to deposit citation data licence-free at Crossref.¹⁸ Beyond that, open source natural language processing tools have become available that can extract and process cited references data directly from source texts with sufficient accuracy, putting the possibility of the creation of citation data into the hands of users.

Such machine learning tools have primarily been designed for classic journal articles. While they perform well for that task, their performance is notably worse (or unknown) for out-of-domain input, that is, documents other than research papers. Here we study the case of the widely used tool GROBID applied to German language research project reports submitted to funders. These reports have highly heterogeneous structure and formatting and initial tests have confirmed that GROBID's performance is degraded relative to documents from within its training domain¹⁹.

We consider research project reports to be part of the 'bibliometric hinterlands'. This concept refers to types of literature that are not themselves research publications but rely on and cite scientific research and which are not commonly charted by science studies. The hinterlands include, for example, trade journals and medical practitioner journals, popular science magazines and online platforms, policy documents of various kinds, patents, and technical standards documents.

¹⁸ <https://i4oc.org/>

¹⁹ <https://open-bibliometrics.de/posts/20251030-TowardsOpenCitationData/>

We study whether it is possible to recover GROBID's reference extraction performance to acceptable data quality levels in this domain by experimenting with adding hand-annotated training data for its `segmentation` and `references-segmenter` models and evaluating extraction performance with domain evaluation data. We did not attempt the next step in the citation extraction pipeline, matching the extracted references to some external corpus.

Method

We work with reports of research projects funded by ministries of the German federal government. These reports are centrally collected by the German National Library of Science and Technology (TIB) (Gabrys-Deutscher & Lütjen, 2022). Over 120,000 electronic reports are freely accessible online.²⁰

GROBID

GROBID is a machine learning tool for the extraction of metadata, specialized for PDFs of academic publications (Lopez, 2009). As a supervised machine learning tool, its performance depends on the amount and quality of training data. In this case, these are hand-annotated XML TEI files. Moreover, the domain of the training data matters. As GROBID is trained primarily on academic journal papers, its performance is high for this domain but may be much lower for different domains, such as project reports. Performance degradation in such domain transfer can be countered by supplying additional training data for the relevant domain and retraining models. Model performance for out-of-domain documents should also be measured with validation data from the new domain.

GROBID is structured as a cascade of mutually dependent models which each perform parts of the total data extraction and where the output of earlier models serves as the input for later models. We only train and evaluate the two models needed for references extraction: the `segmentation` model (splits the text into several main sections); the `references-segmenter` model (splits the reference section into individual cited references, reference texts and reference markers). Optionally, one could also train the `reference` model, which splits reference texts into components such as author names, title, journal title, volume and so on. We decided not to do so because the performance, after improving the other models, was already satisfactory. As we do not need data from tables and figures, we do not train the `fulltext`, `figure`, and `table` models at all. A further consequence of the modularity of GROBID's design is that dependent models are best trained sequentially, rather than in parallel. In our case, as the performance of the `references-segmenter` model depends on the quality of the output of the `segmentation` model, the best course of action was to train the `segmentation` model to saturation, then move on to training the `references-segmenter` model.

²⁰ <https://www.tib.eu/en/search-discover/focus-of-collections/german-research-reports>

We used version 0.8.2 and the included training data, adding the custom training data to the discussed models. We only trained the GROBID CRF models and we used exclusively our custom data for evaluation.

Sample

We sampled project report PDFs from the online catalog of the TIB.²¹ Because it was not possible to directly sample documents, we used the following sampling strategy: We sampled 20 years from the range 1980 to 2024. We restricted results to each year and for each one, we sampled one catalog search result page in the range 1 to 100, as only the first 100 pages are accessible. On each sample page, the PDFs of the ten displayed record were downloaded. We ended up with a sample of 194 files, since not all pages had ten records.

Training and evaluation

Our evaluation strategy was to work with resampling of training and evaluation data and evaluate performance at different training data set sizes. For each training data set size, GROBID models are trained on different random splits of the manually created data into training and evaluation. This gives us several performance measurements at each training set size which together are more informative about the range of achievable performance, rather than a single deterministic measurement. The point of this strategy is to avoid unwarranted certainty. When setting aside a static set of evaluation data, sampling error in the evaluation set may easily lead to results that are unrepresentatively good or bad, a bias which cannot be detected. Sampling repeatedly from a common pool for both training and evaluation is informative of such sampling error and gives useful uncertainty range estimates. We use three runs of different random training/evaluation splits since the training of models takes quite some time. Training documents for the `segmentation` model were created first, the model retrained after this process, and the output used for the training data generation of the `references-segmenter` model.

Findings

The `segmentation` model trained only on the GROBID-supplied training data achieved performance results on 3 runs with 90 randomly selected evaluation records for the `<references>` section of precision (22, 31)% and recall (19, 25)%, reporting the minimum and maximum each. The visualization of F1 scores in Figure 1 shows that supplying domain-specific training data leads to an immediate improvement of performance at with merely 10 and 20 training records. In this and the next figure, black circles are F1 measurements and blue diamonds with error bars are F1 means of three runs with 95% confidence intervals. Increasing training data beyond that point did not lead to any more gains. At 20

²¹ query: identifier:doi:10.2314/{.uri}* supplierPrefix:tibkat documentType:r documentFormat:el. Filters: Licence: Freely available; Language: German

training records, performance is at precision (46, 54)% and recall (34, 49)%. A marked improvement but not good in absolute terms. This means that only about 40% of reference sections are recognized. Of these, about 50% are real reference sections. Detection of other sections of documents for which enough data is available is worse than that for <references>, except for <page> (page numbers).

Figure 1: Evaluation of segmentation model

The `reference-segmenter` model splits the reference section recognized by the segmentation model into individual cited references and each such entry into an optional <label>, the markers used to refer to the reference in the text, and the <reference> itself, the bibliographic information about the cited work. We focus on the latter structure. The model without domain-specific training data performs quite well, see Figure 2. Precision for <reference> is at (60, 72)% and recall at (51, 62)%. Again these minimum and maximum values out of three runs, here with 50 randomly selected evaluation files. Adding domain-specific training data slowly increased performance and no clear leveling off became apparent at 100 training files, which is the upper limit of training files for which reliable evaluation is still possible. At this point, the re-trained model achieves performance of precision: (77, 85)%, recall: (73, 83)%. These measurements were done with 44 evaluation files, as 144 were created in total for this model.

Figure 2: Evaluation of reference-segmenter model

We did not retrain the references model due to its already good performance, which we evaluate with domain-specific data from 46 files without any resampling, see Table 1. Some less important labels are omitted.

Table 1: Evaluation of the references model

label	precision	recall	F1	support
<author>	96.3	96.6	96.4	6343
<booktitle>	86.2	88.1	87.1	2335
<date>	98.5	98.1	98.3	6477
<editor>	84.8	83.7	84.2	532
<institution>	88.8	83.6	86.1	341
<issue>	95.5	94.6	95.0	719
<journal>	93.2	92.5	92.8	3400
<location>	94.9	95.1	95.0	1493
<note>	85.5	84.4	84.9	787
<pages>	96.7	97.7	97.2	4001
<publisher>	90.6	92.9	91.7	1108
<series>	76.0	85.6	80.5	111
<title>	93.4	92.0	92.7	4437
<volume>	96.0	96.6	96.3	3764

Discussion and conclusion

We have carried out experiments on the automated extraction of cited references data from texts belonging to the bibliometric hinterlands, that is, research project reports. These are not original scientific publications but they do contain, besides much formal administrative reporting, usually a summary of the achieved scientific results. Some reports include published papers of manuscripts as annexes. Many reports cite scientific literature, which is one criterion by which they may be described as bibliometric hinterland publications: they are connected to the core scientific citation network in a one-way manner, citing research, but rarely if ever being cited in research publications.

Practical implications

The heterogeneous structure of the reports was a challenge for GROBID. Often these include either no reference list, one reference list not at the very end of the document, or more than one reference list. Footnote references were rare. The correct detection of reference lists was the major difficulty. Retraining with additional domain-specific data did improve performance significantly but not to a high absolute level. On the other hand, the splitting of the reference lists into individual entries by the `reference-segmenter` model worked better and improved consistently, albeit slowly, with additional domain-specific training. It is possible that the model's performance could be increased further than what we achieved with more training data. Moreover, the `references` models, which splits the individual cited reference entry further into fields like authors, journal name, paper title, etc. worked well on our domain-specific evaluation data without additional training. In summary, it is primarily the heterogeneous and idiosyncratic structure of the research reports at the top level that affects the performance of GROBID cited reference extraction. Domain-specific training improves model performance, but not to high absolute levels.

Our performance measurements with domain-specific evaluation data showed significant variability dependent on the particular split of the hand-annotated data into training and text. Using three runs at each training stage showed variability on the order of 10%, which is not negligible at a scale where improvements of 5 or 10% matter. Using one single deterministic training/evaluation split and one run per re-training, one could easily obtain quite misleading results due to sampling error.

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Identifying Citation Elements from Footnotes in Monographs Using Computer Vision and Natural Language Processing Methods

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Keywords

Document Understanding, Citation Extraction, Reference Parsing, Object Detection, Named Entity Recognition.

Purpose of this paper

Bibliographic repositories largely overlook citations embedded in footnotes, despite their prevalence in humanities and social sciences monographs. This results in systematic underrepresentation of book-based citations in bibliographic databases. We present an end-to-end pipeline for detecting, extracting, and parsing bibliographic references from footnotes in scholarly books. Our approach integrates object detection for footnote localisation, OCR-based model for text extraction, and named entity recognition for structured citation parsing. Experiments on a large corpus of open-access monographs demonstrate that relatively small, domain-adapted models deliver strong performance and the entire pipeline substantially outperforms state-of-the-art reference extraction systems. The results demonstrate that automated recovery of footnote-based citations on a large scale is feasible and can significantly improve bibliographic coverage of the literature in the humanities and social sciences.

Introduction

Bibliographic databases such as Web of Science, Scopus, OpenAlex, and OpenAIRE form the backbone of modern research discovery and evaluation. However, their coverage is strongly biased toward journal articles and conference proceedings, while books and book chapters, the dominant publication formats in the humanities and social sciences (HSS) are underrepresented. Large-scale analyses indicate that over 40% of HSS research output appears in monographs or edited volumes, where references are often found in footnotes rather than consolidated bibliographies (Kulczycki 2018). As a result, citations

appearing exclusively in footnotes are therefore omitted from most bibliographic repositories, leading to distorted citation counts and reduced visibility of scholarship in these fields.

Footnotes in monographs present unique challenges for automated processing. Their visual appearance varies considerably across various publishers and disciplines, differing in font size, placement, and column structure. The content of footnotes is also diverse: footnotes may include bibliographic references, commentary, translations, archival identifiers, legal documents, or abbreviated cross-references such as *ibid.* or *ibidem*. Even when they contain scholarly citations, these are often unstructured, incomplete, abbreviated, or multilingual, reflecting disciplinary conventions rather than standardized citation styles (Salager-Meyer 1999; Hammarfelt 2012). Consequently, tools designed for parsing reference lists in journal articles are ineffective when applied to footnote-centric books.

Figure 1 Example of a footnote.

In this article, we address this gap by proposing a dedicated pipeline for extracting citations from footnotes in scholarly monographs. Our approach combines computer vision techniques for page layout analysis with natural language processing methods for structured citation parsing. Unlike prior systems which assume that bibliography sections are clearly separated, our approach explicitly models footnote detection and treats citation parsing as an information extraction task. We demonstrate that this strategy enables the accurate, end-to-end recovery of bibliographic metadata from books in multiple languages.

Related Work

Early work on reference extraction relied primarily on rule-based heuristics tailored to specific citation styles such as those used in journal articles (Peng & McCallum 2004; Lopez 2009). While these approaches are effective in constrained settings, they do not generalize to the stylistic diversity found in humanities literature. Subsequent research introduced probabilistic models, particularly Conditional Random Fields, which became the foundation of widely used systems such as GROBID and CERMINE (Lopez 2009; Tkaczyk et al. 2012 2014, 2015. More recent advances have applied neural architectures, including BiLSTM and Transformer-based models, to improve robustness and accuracy (Cortez et al., 2007; Grennan et al., 2019; Prasad et al. 2018; Ryan, 2018; Tkaczyk et al. 2018).

Despite these developments, most existing systems assume that references appear in a dedicated bibliography section and follow relatively standardized formats. Works that explicitly address footnotes remain limited and typically focus on narrow domains or specific layouts (Rodrigues Alves et al., 2008). In parallel, improvements in OCR and document layout analysis have facilitated text extraction from scanned books, yet footnotes remain problematic due to small font sizes, dense layouts, and frequent multilingual content.

Our work differs from prior approaches in two key aspects. First, we formulate footnote identification as an object detection task, enabling robust localisation regardless of page layout. Secondly, we introduce a dedicated NER-based parsing stage designed for noisy, abbreviated citation strings typical of HSS footnotes. By integrating these components into a unified pipeline, we provide a practical solution for large-scale citation extraction from monographs.

Method

Dataset

The primary data source is the Polish Library of Science²², an open-access repository comprising 1,737 scholarly books. Approximately 38% of the corpus comprises publications in the humanities and social sciences. Most books are written in Polish, with a substantial part in English, although footnotes frequently cite works in multiple languages regardless of the language in which they were published. Additional data sources include the Directory of Open Access Books²³, which contains over 28,085 books in multiple languages, and Polska Bibliografia Naukowa²⁴, which stands for Polish Scientific Bibliography. All selected books allow for derivative works under their licenses.

Two datasets were constructed. The first dataset supports footnote localisation and consists of 7,280 page images that have been manually annotated with bounding boxes indicating footnote regions.

²² <https://bibliotekauki.pl>

²³ <https://doabooks.org/>

²⁴ <https://pbn.nauka.gov.pl>

The second dataset supports citation parsing and comprises over 13,000 extracted footnote entries that have been pre-annotated with the Command R Plus²⁵ model. Out of these 2,662 were manually validated to create high-quality NER training and evaluation data.

Our pipeline consists of three stages: (1) footnote localisation, (2) text extraction and curation, and (3) citation parsing.

Figure 2 Simple pipeline overview.

Footnote Localisation

The issue of footnote localisation is treated as an object detection problem on page images rendered from PDF files. We evaluated several detection architectures, including ResNet-based models (He et al., 2015), MobileNetV3 (Howard et al., 2019), and YOLOv8 variants (Yaseen, 2024). Among the evaluated models (Table 1), YOLOv8n and MobileNetV3 achieved the best overall performances. Errors primarily involved very small footnotes.

Model	mAP	Precision	mAP50	Recall
YOLOv8n	0.896	0.941	0.953	0.906
YOLOv8m	0.864	0.926	0.928	0.873
YOLOv8l	0.858	0.940	0.932	0.845
ResNet18	0.773	0.926	0.773	0.835
ResNet34	0.818	0.866	0.818	0.945
MobileNetV3	0.930	0.954	0.911	0.979

Table 1 Object Detection results for Footnote localisation.

²⁵ <https://huggingface.co/CohereLabs/c4ai-command-r-plus>

Il. 57. Pociąg i znaczka Uniwersytetu Józefa Piłsudskiego z godłem uczelni w indeksie Mieczysława Kudzińskiego z 1935 r., MLUW

Footnote 0.91

Indeks i rocznik Uniwersytetu Warszawskiego, wydanie Wydawnictwa Woteryzacyjnego, s. 105-1939, pieczęć z godłem UW i nakładem „Uniwersytetu Józefa Piłsudskiego w Warszawie”, RP MLUW 127; Indeks Mieczysława Kudzińskiego, wydanie Wydawnictwa Mianowicie-Przyrodniczego (Warszawa), 1935-1939, RP MLUW 967.

Indeks Wydawnictwa Prasa Helony Marii Misoszek, 1936-1939, RP MLUW 752.

którymi uwierzytelniano indeksy studenckie. Wprowadzenie nowej nazwy znalazło oczywiście odzwierciedlenie w treści inskrypcji zamieszczonej w otoku pieczęci, która od 1935 r. brzmiała: **Uniwersytet Józefa Piłsudskiego w Warszawie**. Wydrukowaniu napisu towarzyszyła rezygnacja z umieszczenia daty „MCMXV” oraz pomniejszenie rozmiarów godła⁴¹. Natomiast pod koniec lat trzydziestych znak uniwersytetu w ogóle zniknął z pieczęci uwierzytelniających indeksy i został zastąpiony przez godło państwowe, ale z tym samym co wcześniej napisem w otoku⁴².

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Figure 3 Sample prediction made by fine-tuned YOLOv9 model.

Text Extraction and Curation

Once the footnote regions are detected, the text within them is extracted. For digitally accessible PDFs, text is obtained directly using PyMuPDF²⁶. For scanned or poorly structured documents, OCR is required. We compared traditional OCR engines such as TesseractOCR²⁷, PaddleOCR²⁸ with a vision-language model (VLM) DeepSeekOCR²⁹ on manually curated dataset. The VLM-based approach substantially outperformed standard OCR, achieving over 90% precision and the highest F1 score, particularly for dense and multilingual footnotes.

Extraction Engine	Precision	Recall	F1 Score
PaddleOCR v3	34.90	11.45	16.07
Tesseract v3	59.67	31.21	36.35
Baseline (PyMuPDF)	64.89	53.78	58.55
DeepSeekOCR	92.69	59.01	67.09

Table 2 OCR Evaluation: Quality of raw footnote text extracted from PDF pages.

²⁶ <https://pypi.org/project/PyMuPDF>

²⁷ <https://github.com/tesseract-ocr/tesseract>

²⁸ <https://github.com/PaddlePaddle/PaddleOCR>

²⁹ <https://huggingface.co/deepseek-ai/DeepSeek-OCR>

The extracted text is further curated using lightweight heuristics to merge line fragments, split multiple references within a single footnote, and reassemble footnotes spanning multiple pages.

Citation Parsing

In the final stage, we use named entity recognition to parse footnote text into structured bibliographic components. We have defined fifteen entity classes, including authors, titles, publication years, page ranges, and abbreviated references such as *ibidem*. Due to annotation costs, footnotes were pre-annotated using a large language model and subsequently manually validated. While this approach accelerated dataset creation, manual inspection revealed annotation using an LLM alone is insufficient for high-precision citation parsing.

Figure 4 Sample tagged NER record.

Entity Class	Count
Reference	3329
Author	2872
Pages	2207
PublicationYear	2139
Title	2103
PublicationPlace	760
Ibidem	536
Journal	383
Publisher	331
Editor	325
BookTitle	282
Webpage	260
Issue	205
Volume	197

Translator	96
DOI	17

Table 3 Distribution of entity classes in the manually validated NER dataset.

The manually validated NER dataset is dominated by bibliographic elements such as Reference, Author, Title, and PublicationYear, while low-frequency fields such as DOI and Translator are comparatively rare (Table 3). This skew reflects the typical structure of footnote citations in HSS monographs and highlights the need to evaluate performance beyond overall token-level accuracy, as performance on low-frequency entities can substantially affect downstream BibTeX reconstruction. In practice, some errors in low-support classes can also be mitigated in a later metadata enrichment stage.

Model	Accuracy	Macro Precision	Macro Recall	Macro F1	Weighted F1
XLM-RoBERTa Base	0.979	0.959	0.968	0.964	0.979
BERT Multilingual	0.978	0.951	0.952	0.952	0.978
RoBERTa	0.973	0.924	0.976	0.949	0.973
BERT Uncased	0.974	0.930	0.966	0.947	0.974
DistilBERT	0.974	0.937	0.949	0.943	0.974
SpanBERT	0.969	0.928	0.950	0.939	0.969
mDeBERTa	0.965	0.942	0.915	0.928	0.964
T5	0.972	0.910	0.944	0.926	0.972
ELECTRA	0.951	0.894	0.934	0.913	0.952
CRF	0.827	0.773	0.714	0.739	0.821

Table 4 Model performance for reference detection.

Model	Accuracy	Macro Precision	Macro Recall	Macro F1	Weighted F1
mDeBERTa	0.917	0.804	0.781	0.774	0.917
XLM-RoBERTa	0.920	0.801	0.754	0.761	0.918

Base					
BERT Multilingual	0.919	0.773	0.757	0.751	0.919
RoBERTa	0.883	0.754	0.692	0.703	0.883
ELECTRA	0.863	0.723	0.662	0.686	0.862
BERT Uncased	0.888	0.767	0.650	0.685	0.882
SpanBERT	0.860	0.672	0.576	0.601	0.854
DistilBERT	0.772	0.748	0.536	0.596	0.759
CRF	--	0.540	0.538	0.485	0.485
T5	0.817	0.543	0.398	0.424	0.799

Table 5 Model performance for component classification

We evaluated a range of Transformer-based models and a CRF baseline for both reference span detection (Table 2) and component classification (Table 3). For reference span detection, XLM-RoBERTa Base achieved the best overall results (Accuracy=0.979, Macro F1=0.964, Weighted F1=0.979), with BERT Multilingual performing comparably (Accuracy=0.978, Macro F1=0.952). For component classification, the best Macro F1 was obtained by mDeBERTa (0.774), while the highest Weighted F1 was achieved by BERT Multilingual (0.919) and XLM-RoBERTa Base (0.918). The CRF baseline performs substantially worse than Transformer models in both settings (Macro F1=0.739 for span detection and 0.485 for component classification), and the generative T5 model is competitive for span detection (Macro F1=0.926) but performs poorly for component classification (Macro F1=0.424). However, additional work is needed to better adapt generative models to noisy footnote text and to evaluate them under stronger prompting or fine-tuning. Despite their current performance, generative models offer unique functionality, such as directly producing normalized structured outputs and leveraging richer contextual reasoning for difficult or incomplete references.

Evaluation

We evaluated the entire pipeline using a challenging test set of ten monographs comprising 1,399 manually curated bibliographic entries embedded exclusively within footnotes. Performance was compared against GROBID and CERMINE systems.

For reference string extraction, the baseline systems performed poorly, achieving F1 scores below 0.06. In contrast, our approach achieved an F1 score of 0.767, demonstrating the effectiveness of explicit footnote localisation. In an end-to-end evaluation measuring structured BibTeX extraction, our pipeline achieved an F1 score of 0.790, whereas the baseline systems again failed to produce usable output. These

results confirm that general-purpose reference extraction tools are inadequate for footnote-centric monographs.

System	Precision	Recall	F1
Footnotes	0.671	0.620	0.597
CERMINE	0.201	0.029	0.050
GROBID-CRF	0.219	0.041	0.065
GROBID-DeLFT	0.185	0.034	0.054

Table 6 Reference string extraction performance.

System	Precision	Recall	F1
Footnotes	0.769	0.812	0.790
CERMINE	0.081	0.057	0.010
GROBID-CRF	0.026	0.013	0.018
GROBID-DeLFT	0.068	0.031	0.043

Table 7 End-to-end BibTeX extraction performance.

Findings

We have developed an end-to-end pipeline for extracting bibliographic citations from footnotes in scholarly monographs. Our approach that combines object detection, robust text extraction, and NER-based parsing substantially outperforms existing reference extraction systems when used on books in the humanities and social sciences. Our results demonstrate that automated recovery of footnote-based citations is feasible at scale and can significantly improve bibliographic coverage of book-based scholarship.

Figure 5 View of the application window.

Research limitations/implications

This research is strictly focused on footnotes and references in books. Due to the nature of the source data it focuses on European languages with heavy focus on English and Polish. In future work, we plan to expand the dataset to support more languages and publication traditions, improve the treatment of abbreviated cross-references and scanned documents, and add further metadata enrichment and disambiguation. Ultimately, we aim to develop an end-to-end vision–language model capable of detecting, extracting, and parsing footnote citations jointly.

Practical implications

An open-source tool for running inference with our trained models was also released by us. It supports end-to-end processing of PDF files, producing either an overlay on the original document or structured BibLaTeX file. The tool can also handle *ibidem* references and provides limited metadata enrichment. To support reproducibility, we publish our data and code as open source. Access through GitHub repository³⁰.

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³⁰ <https://github.com/FootnotesExtractor/FootnotesExtractor>

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Mapping Citation Contexts to IMRAD Structure Using Computational Methods

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Keywords

Citation contexts, IMRAD, information extraction, machine learning, BERT, research information systems, bibliometrics

Purpose of this paper

Scientific articles are typically organized according to the IMRAD structure—Introduction, Methods, Results, and Discussion—which encodes a widely shared rhetorical convention for how knowledge claims are introduced, justified and interpreted. Within this structure, citations serve different argumentative roles: they can establish background, justify methodological choices, support empirical findings or situate contributions in ongoing debates. Capturing these differences at scale is essential for making open research information more meaningful to humans and machines alike—for example, by distinguishing citations that ground core methods from those that provide general background.

Our central question is whether vector-based text representations and machine learning models can reliably predict the IMRAD section from which a citation context originates, that is, the sentence in which a reference appears (Small, 1982). To answer it, we systematically evaluate a broad spectrum of representation methods and learning algorithms—from classical bag-of-words to Transformer-based models—on a large annotated corpus, with a particular focus on comparing task-specific BERT-style representations to OpenAI’s embedding models. This design allows us both to test whether citation contexts contain sufficient linguistic and structural cues for accurate IMRAD classification and to assess whether state-of-the-art, off-the-shelf LLM embeddings can approach the performance of fine-tuned models while remaining attractive for deployment in practical citation extraction services.

Method

Dataset

Our experiments rely on the In-text Reference Corpus (InTeReC), which contains 314,023 citation contexts extracted from 90,071 open-access articles published between 2001 and 2013 in seven PLOS journals (Bertin & Atanassova, 2018). Each citation context is linked to its IMRAD section yielding four section labels (Introduction, Methods, Results, Discussion). After removing sentences with overlapping section labels (e.g. “Methods & Results”), the corpus (N = 303,947) exhibits class imbalance, with Discussion sections being most frequent (37.5 %), followed by Introduction (23.5 %), Methods (17.7 %) and Results (9.0 %). The corpus was partitioned into training (80 %) and evaluation (20 %) subsets using a fixed random seed, ensuring that all models are trained and tested on exactly the same instances, which both improves reproducibility and allows for fair comparison across configurations. Note that this corpus reflects a realistic scenario for open research information systems: it is large and heterogeneous across disciplines, and it is derived from publisher XML, which is increasingly available for open-access content. At the same time, it inherits imperfections typical of production data, such as noisy section titles and uneven adherence to the IMRAD convention.

Analysis

In the analysis part of the experiment, each citation context is mapped to a fixed-length vector using one of several representation strategies and then fed into a supervised or unsupervised model that predicts the most likely section label.

On the representation side, we compare:

- Classical vector spaces, such as bag-of-words (**BOW**) and doc2vec-style document embeddings (e.g. the distributed bag-of-words method **DBOW**).
- Large language model embeddings obtained via OpenAI APIs such as “text-embedding-ada-002” (**OAI-2**) and “text-embedding-3-large” (**OAI-3**) (Neelakantan et al., 2022).
- BERT-type transformer representations, including generic pre-trained models (Devlin et al., 2019) and variants fine-tuned either on general tasks (**NLI-ST5**) (Reimers & Gurevych, 2019), **MPNet** (Song et al., 2020) or directly on the **IMRAD** classification task.

On the classification side, we systematically evaluate five families of methods:

- **Linear** classifiers (stochastic gradient descent (Robbins & Monro, 1951), support vector machines (Vapnik, 1963), logistic regression (Berkson, 1944), Ridge regression (Hoerl & Kennard, 1970), and passive-aggressive classification (Crammer et al., 2006)),
- Shallow **neural** networks (perceptron (Rosenblatt, 1958), multilayer perceptron (Rumelhart et al., 1985), and BERT for sequence classification (Sun et al., 2019)),

- **Tree-based** methods (decision trees (Morgan & Sonquist, 1963), random forests (Breiman, 2001), extremely randomized trees (Geurts et al., 2006), and gradient boosting (Friedman, 2001)),
- **Instance-based** methods (K-nearest neighbors (Fix & Hodges, 1951), radius neighbors (Cover & Hart, 1967), nearest centroid (Rocchio, 1971)),
- Unsupervised **clustering** (Gaussian mixture and K-means (Lloyd, 1982)).

This setup produces 172 representation–classifier combinations, but we concentrate on the overarching trends rather than the full score matrix. We evaluate performance with the weighted F1-score to account for class imbalance (see Appendix for detailed results), and then compute medians within each representation and classifier family.

Findings

The experiments confirm that citation contexts carry sufficient linguistic and structural cues to support reliable IMRAD section prediction. Representation–classifier combinations based on a BERT model fine-tuned specifically for IMRAD classification (BERT IMRAD) achieve the best performance, with linear classifiers reaching a median weighted F1-score of 0.753 and neural networks on the same representations close behind at 0.745. Linear models paired with OpenAI’s “text-embedding-ada-002” (OAI-2) also perform strongly (median weighted F1-score \approx 0.711), highlighting that high-quality section prediction is possible both with task-specific fine-tuned models and with general-purpose embeddings.

Table 1. Median weighted F1-score of the classifier types by representation models, ordered, top-down and left-to-right, from the highest to the lowest median of medians.

	<i>IMRAD</i>	<i>OAI-3</i>	<i>OAI-2</i>	<i>Base</i>	<i>Large</i>	<i>NLI-STS</i>	<i>BOW</i>	<i>MPNet</i>	<i>DBOW</i>
<i>Linear</i>	0.753	0.697	0.711	0.696	0.697	0.660	0.624	0.586	0.384
<i>Neural</i>	0.745	0.605	0.651	0.585	0.644	0.618	0.552	0.564	0.381
<i>Tree-based</i>	0.708	0.546	0.519	0.560	0.557	0.506	0.536	0.462	0.360
<i>Instance-based</i>	0.727	0.605	0.561	0.507	0.526	0.543	0.505	0.487	0.371
<i>Clustering</i>	0.645	0.467	0.428	0.440	0.426	0.419	0.360	0.354	0.287

Across representations, domain-specific fine-tuning on the IMRAD classification task consistently achieved the best performance, markedly improving BERT-based models over generic pre-trained or transfer-task-tuned variants. Large language model embeddings from OpenAI—used without any task-specific fine-tuning—are nonetheless competitive: both the older OAI-2 model and the newer embedding (OAI-3) perform well, with OAI-3 yielding better medians across most classifier types,

while OAI-2 remains slightly more effective when combined with the strongest linear classifiers. This pattern suggests that general-purpose LLM embeddings inherently encode document-structural and rhetorical information that can be exploited for IMRAD-aware citation extraction, particularly when fine-tuning resources are limited.

On the classifier side, linear models unexpectedly achieved better results systematically, and outperform neural networks and other classifier families overall, suggesting that, once suitable representations are learned, the IMRAD classification problem is nearly linearly separable. Neural networks rank second, followed by tree-based and instance-based methods, which provide lower performance. Tree-based and instance-based models effectively tie for third place: tree-based classifiers achieve slightly higher median of medians performance (median weighted F1-scores in the 0.36–0.708 range), while instance-based methods perform marginally better when paired with the strongest IMRAD fine-tuned representation (median weighted F1-score ≈ 0.727). In contrast, unsupervised clustering methods yield the weakest results (median weighted F1-scores in the 0.29–0.65 range), underscoring that naive clustering of citation contexts does not align with IMRAD section boundaries and that labelled data are essential for reliable section inference.

Research limitations/implications

This work has several limitations that matter for both interpretation and deployment. It draws entirely on open-access articles from a single publisher (PLOS) over a specific time period, with IMRAD labels derived from XML markup; section conventions, tagging practices, and citation behaviour in other venues or disciplines may differ, so generalisability remains an open question. In addition, we classify each citation-bearing sentence in isolation, without modelling larger discourse units or multi-sentence contexts, which may be necessary to distinguish, for example, conceptual framing, methodological adoption, and critical evaluation.

On the modelling side, performance estimates are affected by class imbalance and by the decision to focus on four “clean” IMRAD labels, leaving other genres (reviews, editorials, policy pieces) and more nuanced citation functions for future work. We also do not yet provide a full engineering assessment of latency, memory footprint, and environmental cost, which is essential before integrating such models into large-scale infrastructures. At the same time, the results have important conceptual implications: they show that task-specific fine-tuning of BERT yields representations in which IMRAD sections are close to linearly separable, that unsupervised clustering is insufficient for recovering section structure, and that modern LLM embeddings can approximate fine-tuned performance “off the shelf.” Together, these findings support the idea that IMRAD-level citation structure is learnable at scale and can be incorporated as an additional layer in citation graphs and research information systems.

Practical implications

For practitioners building citation extraction pipelines and research information systems, the findings suggest a concrete path forward. Existing components for full-text parsing and citation detection can be augmented with an IMRAD classifier of the kind evaluated here, producing enriched citation records in which each in-text reference is tagged with its section-level location. Such records can underpin discovery interfaces that filter by section (e.g. “show studies whose main dataset is cited in Methods”), dashboards that distinguish methodological uptake from discursive mentions, and writing assistance tools that flag atypical or incomplete citation patterns in specific sections.

Because the strongest configurations combine dense embeddings with linear classifiers, they offer an attractive balance between accuracy, efficiency, and transparency, making them suitable for deployment in institutional repositories, open bibliometric platforms, and other resource-constrained environments. Although neural networks are, in principle, more expressive, the fine-tuned embeddings appear to render the problem almost linearly separable, so that convex linear optimization reliably finds a global optimum, whereas neural training might be sensitive to local minima and optimization noise, yielding no expressive gains in this setting. The competitive performance of pre-computed LLM embeddings further enables architectures where large backfiles are embedded once and then served to relatively lightweight models at query time. More broadly, IMRAD-aware citation extraction calls for collaboration between information scientists, NLP researchers, and infrastructure providers to decide how section-level citation information should be stored and exposed—through APIs, metadata schemas, and knowledge graphs—so that users can ask richer questions about the scholarly record while remaining aware of the representational choices and potential biases involved.

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Appendix

Weighted F1-scores for all 172 models combining nine (9) representation techniques and twenty (20) classification methods (Table 2).

Table 2. Table 2. Weighted F1-scores for 172 text-classification models combining representation and classification methods. Rows correspond to twenty classification algorithms, grouped by methodological family and indicated by shades of grey: unsupervised clustering methods (light grey), instance-based classifiers (medium-light grey), linear margin-based and linear probabilistic classifiers (medium grey), tree-based ensemble methods (medium-dark grey), and neural network-based classifiers (dark grey). Columns report nine text representation techniques, including bag-of-words-based representations, doc2vec document embeddings (DBOW method), and transformer-based sentence representations of OpenAI variants and BERT variants. Each cell reports the weighted F1-score obtained for a given classifier–representation combination. Higher values indicate better classification performance. The final row reports performance for an end-to-end fine-tuned BERT for sequence classification. All scores are computed on the same evaluation split and are directly comparable across models.

	Representation type				Representation type (BERT)				
	B	D	O	O	Ba	La	N	M	I
Kmean	0.3408	0.2814	0.4209	0.4700	0.4350	0.4085	0.4220	0.3490	0.6848
Gaussian Mixture	0.3795	0.2919	0.4350	0.4634	0.4447	0.4434	0.4167	0.3599	0.6053
K Neighbors	0.5046	0.3707	0.5902	0.6120	0.6143	0.6115	0.5764	0.5335	0.7274
Radius Neighbors	0.2410	0.2640	0.2051	0.5987	0.2143	0.2148	0.2065	0.4868	0.5050
Nearest Centroid	0.5565	0.3783	0.5609	0.6054	0.5074	0.5264	0.5431	0.4569	0.7319
SVC Linear	0.6283	0.3600	0.7141	0.7018	0.7030	0.7071	0.6746	0.5868	0.7504
SVC RBF	0.6333	0.3993	0.7221	0.7090	0.7110	0.7076	0.6886	0.6275	0.7504
Logistic Regression	0.6345	0.4038	0.7163	0.7044	0.7052	0.7091	0.6782	0.6141	0.7530
Logistic Reg. CV	0.6323	0.4101	0.7163	0.7006	0.7049	0.7094	0.6776	0.6191	0.7525
Ridge Classifier	0.6189	0.3842	0.6938	0.6930	0.6756	0.6813	0.6459	0.5844	0.7526
Ridge Classifier CV	0.6162	0.3841	0.6989	0.6930	0.6752	0.6804	0.6460	0.5856	0.7526
SGD Classifier	0.5532	0.3828	0.6298	0.6474	0.6899	0.6617	0.6392	0.5179	0.7526
Passive Aggressive	0.6015	0.3725	0.7084	0.6639	0.6368	0.6864	0.6101	0.5823	0.7440
Decision Tree	0.5344	0.3360	0.4833	0.5206	0.5148	0.5148	0.4677	0.4264	0.6660
Extra Tree	0.5111	0.3244	0.4331	0.4481	0.4784	0.4812	0.4287	0.3954	0.6690
Random Forest	0.5866	0.3880	0.5554	0.5723	0.6059	0.5992	0.5452	0.4978	0.7479
Gradient Boosting	0.5379	0.3832	0.6328	0.6502	0.6420	0.6402	0.5949	0.5326	0.7515
Perceptron	0.5882	0.3249	0.6578	0.6327	0.5187	0.6323	0.5968	0.5545	0.7361
MLP Classifier	0.5150	0.4362	0.6446	0.5767	0.6522	0.6549	0.6401	0.5733	0.7446
BERT for Sequence									0.7475

Digging Up Citations: FOSSIL, a Dataset and Workflow for Reference Extraction in Law and the Humanities

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Introduction

Citation extraction has been studied extensively (Backes et al., 2024; Cioffi & Peroni, 2022; Colavizza & Romanello, 2017, 2019), but existing models are designed for the structured end-of-document bibliographies typical of the natural sciences. In law and the humanities, scholars continue to cite references primarily in footnotes, where bibliographic data is interleaved with commentary, clarifications, and cross-references, producing highly heterogeneous content that is difficult to parse with standard pattern-based approaches (Boulanger & Iurshina, 2022).

Large Language Models show promise for such heterogeneous data (Sarin & Alperin, 2025; Simons et al., 2026), and even early zero-shot experiments produced strong results on footnote references (“OpenAI (text-davinci-003) reference extraction via API: Code/Result”, 2022). However, closed models depend on third-party infrastructure, are non-reproducible in the long term, and have been decommissioned without notice (Karkee et al., 2025); open-weight alternatives demand dedicated hardware. Meanwhile, LLMs are valuable in human-in-the-loop pipelines, where they accelerate semi-automatic annotation and enable larger datasets at lower cost. The limited availability of specialized gold-standard datasets for SSH literature hampers both the evaluation of LLM based approaches and the training of classical supervised sequence labellers, making the construction of such resources a critical priority.

This work contributes: (i) **PDF-TEI Editor**, a production-ready web based annotation tool; (ii) a documented **annotation workflow** integrating PDF-TEI Editor and Grobid (“GROBID”, 2008–present), carried out by a team of seven; (iii) FOSSIL (Footnote-based Open-access SSH Scientific

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Instance Labels), an openly licensed multilingual dataset of 96 annotated scholarly articles comprising over 7,600 references embedded in footnotes; and (iv) a **Grobid specialization** for law and humanities documents that serves as a proof-of-concept baseline.

Background and related work

Existing SSH-oriented datasets offer complementary but partial coverage. CEX (Cioffi, 2022; Pagnotta, 2024) covers 112 English articles but includes non-openly licensed material. The EXparser Gold Standard (Hosseini et al., 2019) is restricted to 100 German social-science documents. LinkedBooks (Colavizza & Romanello, 2017) provides over 40,000 references from monographs and journals on Venetian history, but remains narrow in domain. Zhu et al. (2026) benchmarked open-weight LLMs against Grobid and found that fine-tuned LLMs are more robust under distribution shift, particularly for non-English and footnote-heavy documents, recommending a routing strategy between Grobid and task-adapted LLMs. FOSSIL addresses remaining gaps by providing an openly licensed corpus that spans multiple SSH disciplines, languages, and citation styles, including the footnote-heavy conventions of law and humanities.

Challenges of citation practices in law and the humanities

In natural-science publications, references form a dedicated section with standardised inline markers, while footnotes are reserved for commentary. In contrast, law and humanities scholarship relies heavily on footnotes to carry bibliographic references alongside commentary, and citation styles vary strongly across languages, disciplines, and journals. Because footnotes are page-scoped, the same reference frequently recurs in shortened form as a cross-reference to an earlier footnote. We identified five recurring footnote content types: (1) comments or clarifications with no reference data; (2) biographical information, typically on the first page; (3) one or more bibliographic references that can be cleanly segmented; (4) cross-references (e.g., “Ibid.”, “See Miller, n.9, p.5”) redirecting to a previous footnote; and (5) mixed content combining all of the above in arbitrary order.

Method

Our approach is grounded in the Grobid architecture: a cascade of specialized machine-learning models extracting and parsing PDF articles into structured TEI-XML. FOSSIL is aligned with this layered design so that annotations can be used independently at each stage or combined end-to-end.

PDF-TEI Editor

We developed an open-source web application supporting iterative, collaborative TEI-XML annotation (Boulanger, 2024–present). It features a synchronized dual-pane PDF/XML view, built-in TEI schema validation, role-based access control, and a plugin architecture that allows integration of arbitrary

extraction backends (currently Grobid and LLaMore (“LLaMore”, 2025–present)). Versioning with branching, merging, and change tracking supports the iterative workflow described below.

Annotation workflow

Source articles were drawn from openly licensed journals listed in DOAJ and CrossRef, strictly excluding non-derivative licences. Documents were organised into ten batches and annotated in five phases: (1) pre-annotation with the latest Grobid model; (2) correction by a first annotator and verification by a second; (3) validation by a senior reviewer; (4) feedback integration into a living annotation guide, with GitHub issues used to track decisions; and (5) training and evaluation of a new model. Seven annotators participated: two senior annotators (the authors), four students from the Digital Humanities Master Program at the University of Stuttgart, and one reviewer. For segmentation, 194 pairwise comparisons on 96 documents yielded a mean Krippendorff’s $\alpha = 0.917$ (median 0.989), indicating reliable agreement, with a clear learning curve across batches.

Dataset

FOSSIL comprises 96 articles from 38 journals in law, humanities, history, and social sciences, with publication dates from 1959 to 2025 and multiple languages (English, Portuguese, Italian, German). The corpus contains approximately 2,400 footnote blocks—about 500 discursive and 1,900 bibliographic—comprising over 7,600 individual references, averaging roughly 100 per document. Annotations are organised in three layers matching the Grobid cascade: article segmentation (structural zones such as `<front>`, `<body>`, `<listBib>`, `<note>`), reference segmentation (splitting content into individual units), and citation parsing (TEI-standard fields extended with a -based encoding for cross-references). The dataset is released both in aggregated form and as separate files per layer.

Grobid specialization

We implemented a specialized processing flow (“flavor”) that incrementally replaces models in the standard Grobid cascade—starting with article segmentation—while reusing the rest of the pipeline. This design follows a principle of maximum reusability and enables targeted evaluation of each replaced component.

Evaluation

We evaluate the trained article segmentation model in isolation and the full specialized pipeline end-to-end against the default Grobid configuration.

Article segmentation

Using 5-fold cross-validation on 96 documents, the specialized segmentation model reaches an overall F1 of 81.08 (Precision 82.91, Recall 79.41). Performance is strong for (86.85), (80.89), and (90.12),

while (78.91), (54.95), and (34.54) are more difficult: these zones share physical page space and can only be distinguished by content, making classification inherently ambiguous.

End-to-end evaluation

To assess the impact of the specialized flow on real world processing, we ran an end-to-end evaluation on four scholarly articles from law and the humanities, previously used to compare an LLM-based extraction library against standard Grobid (see Boulanger, 2026, p. X). Each document was processed through the full pipeline—from PDF to TEI-XML—under two configurations: default Grobid and the specialized “footnotes-ref” flavor. Extracted fields were compared against manually annotated gold-standard references using the LLaMore evaluation framework (“LLaMore”, 2025–present), which computes token-level F1 with fuzzy matching (Levenshtein threshold 0.8) and Hungarian matching for optimal reference alignment. Figure 1 reports per-field F1 for three key fields—journal title, author surname, and publication date—along with micro- and macro-averages.

Figure 1: End-to-end evaluation on author surname, journal title, and publication date, comparing the standard Grobid pipeline and the specialized process that replaces only the segmentation model while reusing the full pipeline.

The default Grobid model shows a highly asymmetric precision–recall profile: precision is high across all three fields (0.89–0.94), but recall is extremely low (0.21–0.27), producing F1 scores between 0.35 and 0.42. This reflects the fundamental mismatch between Grobid’s default training assumptions and footnote based citation styles: the few references it identifies are parsed correctly, but the vast majority of footnote-embedded citations are never recognised as bibliographic content.

The specialized process substantially corrects this imbalance. Recall improves across all fields—from 0.23 to 0.60 for author surnames, 0.27 to 0.73 for journal titles, and 0.21 to 0.71 for publication dates—while precision remains acceptable, yielding F1 scores of 0.67, 0.66, and 0.80 respectively. The micro

averaged F1 rises from approximately 0.36 to 0.72, a near-doubling of extraction quality. The largest gain is on publication date (F1 0.35 → 0.80), reflecting the highly variable date conventions in legal and humanities scholarship (inline parenthetical dates, abbreviated years, dates interleaved with volume numbers). Author surname improves from 0.36 to 0.67, reflecting better handling of abbreviated forenames, particle names, and editorial attributions. Journal title improves from 0.42 to 0.66, consistent with better segmentation of citation strings lacking the explicit delimiters of scientific bibliography styles.

These results confirm that domain-specific specialisation of Grobid’s sequence labelling models substantially improves footnote citation parsing for law and humanities scholarship, while also showing that the primary failure mode— extremely low recall—cannot be addressed by post-processing alone. This motivates the dataset and workflow contributions of this work.

Conclusion and future work

We have presented FOSSIL, together with an annotation tool, a documented workflow, and a Grobid specialization for footnote-based citation practices in law and the humanities. To our knowledge, FOSSIL is the first openly licensed resource of this kind at this scale for legal scholarship, and the end-to-end evaluation confirms substantial gains from domain-specific specialisation (micro F1 from 0.36 to 0.72), while revealing significant headroom, particularly for cross references and mixed-content footnotes. Future work includes extending FOSSIL to additional languages, legal traditions, and historical periods; tackling cross-reference resolution, which remains largely open; and exploring LoRA-based fine-tuning of LLMs (Zhu et al., 2026) as well as end-to-end neural architectures that jointly optimise across article segmentation, reference segmentation, and citation parsing. FOSSIL is intended as a stepping stone toward more expressive models capable of handling the full heterogeneity of SSH citation practices.

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LLM supported reference string recognition and annotation – pilot study with educational research and social science publications

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Keywords

Reference extraction, LLM, GROBID, social sciences, educational sciences

Introduction

The extraction and annotation of bibliographic references are central tasks in the development of open and scalable research information infrastructures (Beyvers et al., 2025; Heibi et al., 2025). Recent advances in large language models (LLMs) offer new opportunities to enhance the efficiency and flexibility of these processes – for an overview see Zhao et al. (2023). Even with minimal fine-tuning, LLMs have demonstrated strong capabilities in identifying, structuring, and validating research information in scholarly documents (cf. Dagdelen et al., 2024). Initial studies focusing specifically on reference annotation indicate promising results, particularly when LLM-based approaches are compared with established state-of-the-art tools such as GROBID (Sarin & Alperin, 2025). These findings suggest that LLMs may enable faster annotation workflows, improved handling of heterogeneous and non-standard citation styles, and more effective human-in-the-loop quality assurance, thereby reducing manual effort while maintaining high annotation quality.

Current reference extraction pipelines in the social sciences typically rely on combinations of tools such as AnyStyle, CERMINE, and GROBID (Lopez, 2009; Cioffi & Peroni, 2022). Backes et al. (2024) provide a comprehensive overview of these tools and evaluate various combinations within the OUTCITE pipeline for extracting references from social science publications (Hosseini et al., 2019).

Their results indicate that workflows combining pdftotext, GROBID, and AnyStyle achieve the most robust performance for the evaluated datasets. Recent studies, such as Zhu et al. (2026), highlight the limitations of current parsing and end-to-end processing methods, finding that GROBID excels with well-structured PDFs, while leveraging LLMs demonstrate greater robustness; they propose a hybrid strategy combining GROBID with Low-Rank Adaption (LoRA) fine-tuned LLMs for enhanced performance, particularly with complex Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) documents. Moreover, the study by Zhu et al. (2026) compared the pipeline GROBID with different LLMs and concluded that the latter show greater robustness e.g. with complex layouts.

Method

Building on these findings, the project *Open Citation Data for Educational Research* (OFFZIB) (Weimer et al., 2025) investigates suitable approaches for extracting reference data from educational research publications hosted in the open-access repository peDOCS³². During the preparation of manually curated gold-standard datasets for tool evaluation, ChatGPT was employed to support the reference annotation process, revealing considerable potential for LLM-assisted workflows. The present study constitutes a follow-up that systematically examines these initial observations.

This paper investigates how generative LLM can support tasks in the processing of research information in scholarly documents: (1) extracting references, and 2) assisted reference annotation, including the labelling of reference fields such as authors. The underlying approach conceptualizes LLMs as human-in-the-loop accelerators that generate annotation proposals and normalize reference strings, while expert validation ensures reliability and reproducibility.

The study addresses the following research questions:

- (1) How effectively can LLM extract references in educational research and social science publications?
- (2) How accurately can LLM annotate reference data from educational research and social science publications across relevant reference fields?

The present study applies data from peDOCS and the educational domain as well as from EXCITE³³, which contains documents from Social Science Open Access Repository (SSOAR)³⁴. It compares reference extraction by LLMs and compares the results with a manually annotated gold standard and the applied project baseline, which is GROBID. It adapts the approach by Zhu et al. (2026) to compare the results from disciplinary domains. Moreover, the main database in the OFFZIB project, peDOCS, includes heterogeneous educational research publications encompassing multiple document types,

³²<https://www.pedocs.de/>

³³<https://github.com/exciteproject>

³⁴<https://www.ssoar.info/ssoar/>

including journal articles, conference proceedings, anthologies, reviews, and reports, as well as diverse citation styles. This makes exact reference extraction challenging.

In the current study, prompting strategies are developed and iteratively refined using the original data. The prompt provides detailed semantic instructions for field labeling without the use of examples. The best-performing prompt is then applied to the subsamples. In compliance with German copyright law, we need to take care of the peDOCS data used for testing the LLMs. Therefore, we will chose LLMs hosted on institutional instances within Germany. For the EXCITE dataset, an external model hosted by OpenAI like GPT-5.1 can be applied.

To test the larger EXCITE dataset, a python pipeline has been developed that automates the file upload and the prompting at the Open WebUI³⁵. For testing, the gpt-oss:120b and the gpt-5.1 LLM model has been used with a 64,000 token context window, a temperature of 0.8 and top_k of 40. The models are provided with the full text of the publication to ensure maximum contextual awareness during processing. The raw model output is parsed using regular expression-based extraction to isolate structured XML tags.

The evaluation assesses annotation quality and the validity of LLM-assisted workflows, with a particular focus on their integration into human-in-the-loop processes for reference extraction in educational research. Therefore, we apply manually annotated datasets. The EXCITE gold standard (n = 348) is published on GitHub³⁶ and was used in Backes et al. (2024). To measure the performance, we use the F1-score to evaluate annotation accuracy across primary bibliographic fields (author, title, and source etc.).

Practical Implications

The results will contribute to systematically analyse new approaches of reference extraction and provide practical guidance for researchers selecting suitable models and methods for large-scale reference extraction and annotation tasks.

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³⁵<https://docs.openwebui.com/>

³⁶https://github.com/exciteproject/EXgoldstandard/tree/master/Goldstandard_EXparser

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Detecting and Classifying Publications based on their Abstracts with LLM Embeddings and Multi-Label Classifiers

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Keywords

LLM, citations, Multi-Label Classifiers

Introduction

The ever-growing volume of publications makes organizing, analyzing, and navigating them increasingly difficult. Automated methods promise to ease this workload, usually by providing a form of pre-selection or ranking. The information contained in a citation network built on the citation data of the publications is a prime candidate for such methods:

Citations infer topical proximity, familiarity, and the lineage of science. They induce a simple binary and asymmetric relation (where a *cites* b), which serves as input to algorithms on graphs. Many well-established methods, such as the Leiden algorithm (Traag et al., 2019) and PageRank (Brin and Page, 1998, Chen et al., 2023), operate on this premise. Texts of the publications themselves would naturally contain the largest share of information; however, they are shrouded by semantics and not as easily parsed into a machine-readable form. This challenge is addressed by natural language processing (NLP),

most recently through advances via large language model (LLM) embeddings. Beyond retrieval and unsupervised methods (Keraghel et al., 2024), LLM-embeddings are inherently well-suited for supervised classification. In this work, we built classification methods for publications based on their abstracts from the Web of Science (Clarivate, n.d.), via LLM-embeddings. These classifiers predict the topic of an unknown publication, enabling both the automated labeling of large datasets and the analysis of citation-linkage of semantically proximate publications.

Method

LLM-embeddings map texts of any given length and content to a single point in a high-dimensional vector space. This mapping can capture even smaller semantic differences, as it is based on the comprehensive training of the underlying model on large bodies of text. As a result, the output, a simple vector of length usually between 768 and 4096, is small enough to allow handling datasets from thousands to millions of data points, such as the publication database Web of Science (WoS). If we compare this format to that of a citation network, the resulting set of vectors can be interpreted in multiple ways:

- Instead of a binary, asymmetric relation (such as a cites b), each metric in the vector space gives us a precise number of the distance between two publications a and b . In this way, we obtain a numerical representation of the similarity or closeness of a and b .
- All vectorized abstracts combined reveal a self-structured landscape of texts, a map of sciences, as described in our previous work (Kunt et al., 2025).
- Embedding vectors serve as fitting input for prevalent classification and prediction methods from machine learning, both as a data type and due to them containing the semantic contents in a compressed, yet expressive form.

Figure 1: Positive correlation of the distances in the embedding space and on the citation graph (see also [Kunt et al., 2025]): For this plot, we randomly sampled 100,000 pairs of publications from the Web of Science dataset and computed the shortest path on the complete citation graph, as well as the cosine distance in the embedding space.

Citations and proximity in the embedding space, however, encode two fundamentally different relationships. Citations reflect influence, academic genealogy, peers and institutions; in general, the structures and most importantly time and progress. Proximity in the embedding space reflects semantic similarity, which in turn describes shared language, shared topics, and shared views. Proximity in the citation network and proximity in the embedding space correlate (as illustrated by fig.1), but they are not equivalent.

Experiments

Building on our previous study (Kunt et al., 2025), we consider the abstracts of 416, 540 publications from WoS and their embeddings. Full-texts are not available for all publications. We also argue that embedding the abstracts serves as a good compromise between computational resources and expressiveness. Abstracts explicitly summarize the intent, scope, methods, and conclusions of their publication. This descriptive quality makes them a well-suited text form for LLM-embeddings.

We use the *mxbai-embed-large:335m* embedding model with 1,024 dimensions (Mixedbread AI, 2024) inside an ollama framework. For a discussion of the model choice and comparison with *nomic-embed-text:v1.5* (Nomic AI, 2024), we refer to our previous study.

As input for training, we choose the *traditional subject* labels by WoS. These labels assign each publication one or more subjects from a list of 255, as classified by WoS. Note that most publications are assigned to multiple subjects, and many of the subjects appear to have overlaps and/or are contained in one another.

With the embeddings and the subject labels set, we can implement supervised learning methods. For this, the different subject labels serve as input for multi-output regression models. We run a ridge regression as a strong baseline and linear model, in addition to a random baseline for reference. Further, we implement two multilayer perceptron (MLP) architectures with Keras to grasp more complex and non-linear relationships between the data points:

- **MLP I** contains an input layer and a single hidden densely-connected ReLU layer of 100 neurons, followed by an output layer with 254 neurons and softmax activation. We use Adam optimizer and evaluate by classification accuracy. Training runs for 100 epochs, however we also run MLP I with early stops to avoid overfitting and reduce unnecessary training time.
- **MLP II** contains four hidden densely-connected ReLU layers with 512 neurons each. To avoid overfitting and accelerate training, we employ *L2* regularization and batch normalization. MLP II uses Adam too, but adds a learning rate scheduler. We train for max. 200 epochs with early stopping enabled.

MLP I constitutes a simple network architecture, MLP II scales and serves as a test to exhaust the capabilities of this approach or to verify that a simpler model may be adequate. Both the regression model and the MLPs are built to output a vector of subjects, where each potential subject is assigned a weight between 0 and 1. This expresses both the confidence with which the models predict the subject and its belongingness to one or multiple subjects. For all models, the data is divided into a 9 : 1 train-test split. As a comparison and to detect overfitting, we run the same models on a smaller sample of 41, 901 publications. Computations run on an Intel Xeon CPU E3-1270 v6 (3.80GHz) with a Nvidia Quadro P400.

Discussion

Assessing the predictive qualities of the proposed models merely by numbers, i.e., by evaluating measures of accuracy, hardly does this analysis justice, or as (Held et al., 2021) states: “*Topics as collectively shared perspectives on knowledge cannot be used as ground truths for assessing the outcomes of bibliometric topic reconstruction exercises because the former is an interpretive scheme embedded in human consciousness and the latter is a structured set of publications.*” A thorough qualitative analysis, however, exceeds the scope of this extended abstract and will be the subject of the accompanying talk.

The following table summarizes the results of our supervised learning approach, comparing the different methods by computational time and error metrics on the test-set. For mean squared error (MSE), we

compare the predicted subject vectors on the test set with the WoS *traditional subject* labels. Further, we compute the mean reciprocal rank (MRR), which compares the list of predicted subjects descending by the value assigned by the classifier to the list of *traditional subject* labels. Best performing classifiers for each measure are highlighted in bold.

Sample Size	Classifier	Time	MSE	MRR
41, 901	Random Baseline	-	0.0028	0.0278
41, 901	Ridge Regression	153.66s	0.0023	0.6249
41, 901	MLP I	467.98s	0.0025	0.5867
41, 901	MLP I (early stop)	98.20s	0.0020	0.6431
41, 901	MLP II (early stop)	165.64s	0.0021	0.6427
416, 540	Random Baseline	-	0.0027	0.0297
416, 540	Ridge Regression	66.31s	0.0022	0.6361
416, 540	MLP I	5517.09s	0.0020	0.6593
416, 540	MLP I (early stop)	934.92s	0.0020	0.6672
416, 540	MLP II (early stop)	21772.79s	0.0019	0.6766

Due to the clear structure of the data points in the embedding space, the regression baseline already performs as a strong linear predictor. The MLP models outperform across the evaluated metric MRR. Note that results of MLP II on the smaller dataset are included for completeness, however showcases overfitting, as is to be expected at this size.

A qualitative analysis reveals that when the predictors deviate from the WoS labels, they mostly agree on the broader topic but differ in a finer distinction to the field, especially for subjects that overlap. For instance, consider the labels *Multidisciplinary Physics*, *Applied Physics*, and *Physics of Fluids and Plasmas*, all of which are parts of *Physics* but mutually intersect. In such cases, the predicted labels and WoS labels may differ. Likewise, we observe that the performance differs between branches of science, with certain subjects in the humanities proving harder to distinguish from one-another. Many of the mismatching prediction labels appear to be improvements or corrections on the original labeling. This is particularly apparent for publications, mislabeled in the WoS database due to their journal-level labeling scheme categories (Clarivate, 2025). The classifiers proved to provide better estimates, for the aforementioned publications, of the corresponding subjects over WoS. To conclude, the experiments showcased that the automated classification scheme based on validated training labels is a robust method for structuring publication data to a finer degree. Our future works aim at scaling these experiments on the entire WoS dataset, as well as comparing the results to an implementation on the OpenAlex database (Priem et al., 2022).

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Bibliographical Parsing of Descriptive Linguistic Literature

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Keywords

LLM, citation extraction, bibliographical parsing

Purpose of this paper

Descriptive Linguistics is the sub-domain of Linguistics which is concerned with the description and comparison of the diversity of the approximately 7,000 languages of the world. This domain includes grammars, dictionaries, sociolinguistic studies, phonologies, comparative studies, overviews and so on with bibliographies of varying lengths. Extracting the bibliographies is useful for information retrieval, bibliometrics, and analysis/coverage of the field itself. In this paper we describe the parsing of some 40,000 documents (Virk et al., 2020) far more diverse in bibliography styles, citation practices, language and OCR quality than many other domains. Existing CRF tools fall short of completing the task without additional targeted training data. Hence we revive the classic RegExp technology for better control and consistency across the heterogeneities. Bibliography extraction proceeds in two steps: Bibitem identification and parsing. In identification, author-year-title signatures are used to locate potential bibitems whether they occur inline or collected in a bibliography listing at the end of a document. Parsing is more a matter of covering a wide range of styles and variation, and here our domain is a considerable challenge covering a range of styles over some fifty languages, several centuries, a dozen writing systems, five calendar systems and so on. Over a million references tokens corresponding to over 600,000 unique references were extracted and parsed resulting in by far the argest bibliography of this domain, notwithstanding many errors and imperfections that still remain to be addressed. Some partial measures of evaluation are discussed including comparison to the largest human-curated bibliography in the same domain (glottolog.org) and the comparison between citations and references within the same document. The output of the RegExp based extraction is useful in itself or training/test data serving a neural or probabilistic system.

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Open Social Science Citation Index (OpenSSCI) – A Dataset of Metadata and Citation Links from SSOAR produced by the OUTCITE Project

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Keywords

References, reference extraction, bibliographic metadata, citations, bibliometrics, information retrieval, open citations, Open Access repository, metadata normalization, reference parsing, dataset, open science.

Purpose

The increasing availability of open citation data has enabled major advances in scholarly search, bibliometric analysis, and citation-based recommender systems. However, social sciences remain underrepresented in many of these datasets, particularly when it comes to references extracted from full-text sources in disciplinary repositories. Many publishers strive to index their publications to bibliographic databases, enabling the linking of publications in a citation graph. Still, a significant part of citation data in disciplines such as social science is not accessible via bibliographic databases. To address this gap, we present the Open Social Science Citation Index (OpenSSCI): A Dataset of Metadata and Citation Links from SSOAR³⁷ (Social Science Open Access Repository) produced by the OUTCITE Project [1] from over 63,000 full-text documents processed until November 26, 2025.

Method

The references were extracted directly from PDF full texts, so we had to deal with all the usual inconsistencies: missing identifiers, inconsistent formatting, and lots of noise. We used a combination of tools [2] for extraction, and parsing. Later, performed a rule-based handling for mapping and cleanup to meet the requirements for OpenCitations as stated in [3]. OpenSSCI contains more than 2.3 million structured reference entries and over 3.1 million directed citation links, all extracted, and parsed using a pipeline [2] developed as part of the OUTCITE³⁸ project at GESIS. The dataset is validated using

³⁷ <https://www.gesis.org/ssoar>

³⁸ <https://demo-outcite.gesis.org/>

oc_validator³⁹ for downstream ingestion into OpenCitations⁴⁰. The OpenSSCI dataset is openly available on Zenodo under a CC0 license⁴¹. The goal was to create a clean, structured, and openly available resource that helps researchers and developers work on reference parsing, linking, normalization, and bibliometric analysis. Furthermore, GESIS search⁴² utilizing OUTCITE references and citation links. You can view an example by visiting a webpage⁴³ for a demo document.

Dataset

The dataset includes two primary components: a metadata.csv file containing detailed bibliographic information for cited works as shown in Table 1, and a citations.csv file listing citing–cited document pairs along with their publication years as displayed in Table 2. For full details on the CSV schema and fields, see the OpenCitations GitHub documentation [3].

metadata.csv — one row per reference

Bibliographic metadata for each referenced item extracted from SSOAR documents. Contains 2,306,779 validated references with fields including: id, title, author, pub_date, venue, volume, issue, page, type, publisher, and editor.

id	title	author	pub_date	venue	volume	issue	page	type	publisher	editor
doi:10.3386/w9305	Institutions Rule: The Primacy of Institutions over Geography and Integration in Economic Development	Rodrik, D; Subramanian, A; Trebbi, F	2004	Journal of Economic Growth	9	2	131-165	journal article		

Table 1: Example record from metadata.csv

citations.csv — one row per citation link

Directed links from each citing SSOAR document to its cited reference. Contains 3,126,779 citing–cited ID pairs, along with the corresponding publication dates (citing_publication_date, cited_publication_date).

citing_id	citing_publication_date	cited_id	cited_publication_date
doi:10.37043/JURA.2011.3.1.3	2011		2004

³⁹ https://github.com/opencitations/oc_validator

⁴⁰ <https://opencitations.net/>

⁴¹ <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/legalcode>

⁴² <https://search.gesis.org/>

⁴³ <https://search.gesis.org/publication/gesis-ssoar-86950>

		doi:10.3386/w9305	
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Table 2: Example record from citations.csv

Research Contribution

This contribution is highly relevant to the workshop's goals: Making bibliographic data available is important in all disciplines to ensure easy and fast access to literature and other scientific resources such as research datasets. This dataset feeds validated reference metadata and citation links from SSOAR for ingestion into OpenCitations, enabling open, reproducible citation analysis and supporting research in bibliometrics, IR, and open science by offering a reusable dataset.

Future Work

Looking ahead, we plan to produce new dataset like OpenSSCI by integrating data from other repositories such as peDOCS⁴⁴. We also aim to feed this data into OpenCitations. We believe that by making citation data from the social sciences and educational sciences more accessible and machine-readable (AI-ready), we can help in opening new doors for research, reproducibility, and better tools for navigating scholarly knowledge. Large language models (LLMs) could significantly enhance automated reference extraction and linking by improving the contextual understanding of citations [4], enabling more accurate disambiguation of incomplete or inconsistently formatted references. Additionally, LLMs may facilitate adaptive, cross-domain linking by leveraging semantic similarity and external knowledge, potentially reducing reliance on rigid rule-based or template-driven systems.

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⁴⁴ <https://www.pedocs.de/>